

INVESTIGATIONS OF SOLAR WIND PARAMETERS BASED ON MULTI-SATELLITE OBSERVATIONS FROM THE FIRST LAGRANGIAN POINT OF THE SUN-EARTH SYSTEM.

Thesis submitted to the Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India in the partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of Masters of Technology in Space and Atmospheric Science.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the Project Report entitled “**Investigations of Solar Wind Parameters based on multi-satellite Observations from the First Lagrangian Point of the Sun-Earth System**” submitted for the fulfilment of the Masters of Technology (M.Tech), in Space and Atmospheric Science, is an original work carried out by me, under the guidance and supervision of Prof. Dibyendu Chakrabarty, Space and Atmospheric Science Division, Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad, India, and Dr. Kalyan Bhuyan, Dept. of Physics, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh, Assam, India. The work incorporated here is original and not copied from any other source. The source of literature or any information derived from the existing literature has been indicated throughout the report at appropriate places.

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Abstract

Space weather refers to the variations in the particle, radiation, and electromagnetic field environments due to the Sun, which impacts the interplanetary medium, magnetosphere, radiation belt, thermosphere and ionosphere. These variations occur during solar flares, and during the passage of coronal mass ejections (CMEs), corotating interaction regions (CIRs), etc. through the interplanetary medium. The disturbances on the Sun and in the interplanetary medium can affect radio communication and maritime applications, cause power grid failure, impact astronaut safety, and cause satellite degradation and damage. Modelling and predicting the impact of space weather and its early forecast can help mitigate such problems.

CMEs, large solar eruptions from the Sun, take about two to three days to reach the Earth, though all CMEs do not cause geomagnetic storms; it depends on the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) and its orientation. CIRs can also cause moderate geomagnetic storms. A comparative study of these solar events for solar cycle 24 is carried out in this work. A two-point multi-satellite correlation length and decorrelation length between the satellites ACE and Wind at the Sun-Earth L1 position are measured for various solar parameters, e.g., IMF components, solar wind proton density, proton velocity, and alpha-proton density ratio.

The correlation length quantifies the distance between two data points from the satellites at which a physical quantity maintains its correlation. This definition mathematically characterises the statistical dependence of a physical quantity at two points separated by a distance R_E , where correlation persists. The correlation coefficient can be analysed to derive insights into solar wind scale lengths and to assist in forecasting space weather using satellite monitors. According to the study, CMEs have the largest correlation length and the ambient solar wind has the lowest correlation length, while CIRs exhibit a moderate correlation length during solar cycle 24. According to the analysis of the various phases of solar cycle 24, the correlation length is largest for solar maximum and lowest for solar minimum. Further, the correlation lengths in solar cycle 24 are higher during the descending phase of the solar activity than during the ascending phase.

Keywords: Solar wind, IMF, Space weather events, correlation/decorrelation length, geoeffectiveness.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS:

ACE- Advanced Composition Explorer
Amb – Ambient Solar wind
CIR – Corotating Interaction Region
CME – Coronal Mass Ejection
DST- Disturbed Time Index
EUV - Extreme ultraviolet
FC - Faraday Cup
FFT – Fast Fourier Transformation
GGS - Global Geospace Science
HSS- High-speed stream
ICME - Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection
IMF – Interplanetary Magnetic Field
L1 – First Lagrangian Point
MAG - Magnetic Field Experiment
MC – Magnetic Cloud
MFI - Magnetic Field Investigation
MHD – Magnetohydrodynamics
 N_p – Proton Density
nT – nano Tesla
PSD – Power Spectral density
 R_E – Earth Radii
SIR – Stream Interaction Regions
SWE - Solar Wind Experiment
SWEPAM - Solar Wind Electron Proton Alpha Monitor
SWICS - Solar Wind Ion Composition Spectrometer
SWIMS - Solar Wind Ions Mass Spectrometer
UV – Ultraviolet
 V_p – Proton Speed
 λ_c - Correlation length
 λ_d - decorrelation length

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Chapter 1:

Introduction:

The Sun, the prime energy source, constantly emits electromagnetic or corpuscular radiation into the interplanetary medium. Radiation from the Sun influences the Earth and the entire solar system. The steady flow of plasma from the Sun to the interplanetary medium due to pressure gradient is called solar wind. The most important large-scale features in the interplanetary medium are the coronal mass ejections (CMEs). CMEs are large, sudden outbursts in the solar corona, facilitated by the Sun's magnetic field causing an enormous release of energy and mass. CMEs are the main drivers of space weather and highly impact the terrestrial environment [Vourlidas et al., 2012]. The "Space weather" science aims to comprehend how solar-terrestrial interaction affects society and technology [Moldwin, 2008]. Space weather is the manifestation of the Sun-Earth interaction, involving the impact of solar flares, Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs), etc. on the magnetosphere, radiation belt, and ionosphere [Moldwin, 2008]. The effect of space weather on the present space-based technologies is enormous. The radiation from the Sun can damage or destroy satellites, communication, navigation, and power grid failure affecting the astronaut's safety. In the last few decades, our society has become more dependent on satellites for global communication and navigation. So, modelling and predicting the impact of space weather and early forecasts help mitigate such problems.

In the presence of multiple satellites, the success of the satellite monitoring of the solar wind parameters from the L1 point depends on two aspects: one, the consistency of the measured parameters, which, in turn, depends on the inter-calibration between the satellites, and two, the inherent spatial inhomogeneity of the measured parameters between the satellites due to physical processes.

An in-depth investigation of solar wind parameters reveals a strong correlation between solar activity and solar wind variability. Sunspot formation is one of the visible indicators of solar activity connecting to strong solar events like solar flares and coronal mass ejections, both of which significantly influence the solar wind.

Examining solar wind variability and its possible consequences on the space environment of Earth relies on an in-depth understanding of sunspot activity.

Sunspots are black regions on the photosphere, the Sun's outer layer, results due to strong magnetic activity, which prevents convection close to the surface of the Sun. The darker regions of the sunspots is because their temperature is lower than that of their surroundings.

Sunspots appear over a large range of latitudes on either side of the Sun's disk in the 11-year solar cycle. Generally, as the cycle goes along, they move equator-wards after first appearing around about $\pm 30^\circ$ N/S latitude. Flares, filament eruptions, and coronal mass ejections are more common during solar maximum. These phenomena are connected with substantial variations in solar ultraviolet and extreme ultraviolet radiation and are accompanied by material losses to space. An increase in the sunspot number is correlated with increased solar activity. The most important

object of future research is directed toward more accurate predictive models of solar events time, and effects, improving knowledge about the solar wind [Zhang et al., 2023].

Figure 1.1, depicts a schematic butterfly diagram showing the latitudinal migration of sunspot emergence over about 11 years; which marks one solar cycle. This diagram shows how variation in the latitudinal extent of sunspot emergence is associated with fluctuation in solar activity [Norton et al., 2023].

A key objective of understanding solar wind dynamics is to develop forecasting tools that will enable proactive measures to prevent or minimize adverse effects on space-

Fig 1.1: Schematic of butterfly diagram (above) and 11-year solar cycle phenomenon (below) [https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/SunspotCycle.shtml.]

bound and terrestrial systems, improve preparation for critical infrastructure security, and foster resilience in an increasingly interconnected world.

1.1 The Solar Wind:

The Sun consists of several significant layers, which vary in the different roles played in the working of the Sun: the core, where nuclear fusion occurs with extreme pressure and heat, drives the nuclei of hydrogen into helium, and vast amounts of thermal energy are released in this process called the proton-proton (p-p) chain. Following is the radiative zone, where radiation is generated, slowly and gradually, from the energy released by nuclear fusion reactions. Then there is the tachocline: a transitional region wherein the interior parts of the Sun show differential rotation, thus creating a complex magnetic field. These extend outward to reach the convective zone, where convective currents carry energy outwards to the surface.

The photosphere is the outermost layer of the solar atmosphere. It appears granular because of the Sun's convection currents. These enormous bubbles of hot plasma form a dynamic, ever-changing surface by rising, cooling, and falling again. Sunspots, faculae, and solar flares are the most common solar events. The chromosphere, a layer filled with dynamic features, lies above the photosphere but beneath the corona and the solar transition region. Spicules, which are jet-like plasma structures, are examples of such dynamic features.

The solar wind releases charged particles from the Sun's outer atmosphere's corona, primarily protons, and electrons with a small amount of heavier ions. E. N. Parker first proposed the concept of solar wind in 1958 [Parker 1958]. Direct readings from the Mariner 2 spacecraft later proved its validity. The solar corona retains temperatures greater than a million Kelvin. The pressure difference between the corona and the local interstellar medium is sufficiently large to drive the plasma outwards against the Sun's gravitational pull.

The ambient solar wind is called the continuous flow of charged particles, mostly protons and electrons, from the Sun's outer atmosphere, known as the corona. It flows through the solar system, influencing space weather and interacting with the planetary

magnetospheres and ionosphere. Two kinds of solar winds have been identified: fast solar winds and slow solar winds.

High-speed solar wind originates primarily in regions called coronal holes. These regions occur at latitudes greater than 30 degrees North/South and emit a cooler version of solar wind. The fast solar wind has temperatures of less than 1 million Kelvin at its source and closely mimics the composition of the photosphere.

The slow solar wind travels at speeds of less than 400 km/s and is hotter, with temperatures of more than 1.2 million Kelvin at its source. It is concentrated closer to the equatorial plane, especially towards lower latitudes within 30 degrees North/South latitude. It is significantly more diverse in composition, with higher percentages of heavier ions.

Because solar wind impacts the space environment where satellites and spacecraft operate, protecting technological infrastructure is crucial for space exploration. Continuous research and observation help scientists better predict and mitigate the effects of solar wind upon our technological society.

1.2 Coronal Mass ejection (CME):

The first optical observation of a CME was made on 14th December 1971, using the coronagraph of the Orbiting Solar Observatory 7 (OSO-7) by R. Tousey of the Naval Research Laboratory, in 1973. Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) are substantial eruptions of high-energy plasma expelled from the Sun's outer atmosphere, the corona, into interplanetary space. CMEs are enormous explosions formed at the solar corona which carry high-energy plasma into space. This produces in interplanetary space on average 10^{31} ergs of kinetic energy [Webb and Howard, 1994]. The CMEs discharge protons, electrons, and other heavier ions like helium, iron, oxygen, and other elements. Usually ranging from several 100 km/s to more than 2000 km/s, occasionally even up to 3000km/s, CMEs consist of magnetic field flux ropes.

Most CMEs originate from the solar corona; they are closely connected to the solar cycle, correspond with sunspot count, and peak at solar maximum. A solar flare is

usually caused by an eruption of the Sun, which produces massive amounts of electromagnetic radiation spanning the spectrum from radio waves to gamma rays.

The interplanetary CME traveling through the interplanetary medium is called an ICME. Typically, the ICME is divided into three separate regions, including the shock, the sheath, and the magnetic cloud [Rouillard, 2011]; however, such features differ from one ICME to another. Figure 1.2 demonstrates the schematic diagram of the ICME structure [Zurbuchen and Richardson, 2006].

Fig 1.2: Schematic of an ICME revealing the shock, sheath, and magnetic cloud regions. [Zurbuchen and Richardson, 2006]

The structure of ICME consists of:

1. **Shock Region:** This is a shock front of the ICME compressing plasma in the region with magnetic fields as the CMEs travel at supersonic speeds that engulf the solar wind.
2. **Sheath Region:** The sheath region comes immediately after the shock wave. It is a highly compressed material with turbulence. Magnetic fields here become stronger and fluctuate which enhances the proton solar wind density due to higher velocity, dynamic pressure, and temperature. The plasma becomes highly heated and compressed due to the interaction between the CME and the surrounding solar wind [Gosling and McComas, 1987].
3. **Magnetic cloud (MC):** Magnetic clouds are more organized and orderly than the sheath region. The region is characterized by tightly twisted internal helical magnetic field lines known as flux rope structures. As a result, it creates a denser and colder environment compared to the sheath area. This region can significantly affect the Earth's magnetosphere.

CMEs and their interplanetary counterparts, ICMEs, are regarded as precursors of space weather. When an ICME hits the magnetosphere of Earth, it produces geomagnetic storms and auroras, interrupting satellite and communication

systems. The rising and varying magnetic fields in the sheath, which produce the resultant high dynamic pressures, compress the magnetosphere and create large electric currents in the ionosphere.

It is essential to understand CMEs and ICMEs to comprehend how the Sun affects the heliosphere and shields Earth and space systems from possible disruptions. Further observation and study are thus required to enhance our understanding as well as our predictive ability for these high-energy solar outbursts. Previous research has shown that solar flares, filament eruptions, and coronal mass ejections grow stronger during the solar maximum period. Differences in solar UV and EUV radiation and coronal ejections from the sun are the major features of these events. A higher number of sunspots indicates increased solar activity [Duraïd et al., 2018].

CMEs can be described as eruptions including a twisted flux rope from an erupting filament. Closed magnetic field lines keep this filament in equilibrium until a magnetic instability causes it to erupt in the form of the flux rope [Wang et al., 2017]. Cold, dense prominence material enveloping the CME is formed from hot plasma. Closed magnetic fields exist within the exploding region above the prominence, creating a magnetic flux rope that extends into the interplanetary medium.

A halo CME is a coronal mass ejection directly headed toward Earth. The term is derived from its behaviour since it points either directly away from or is pointing toward the observer, literally appearing like an actual halo. Hence, CMEs, sometimes called halos from Earth, are most likely to significantly impact geomagnetic activity. Employing geomagnetic indices like the Dst index and the K_p index, one can quantify the geomagnetic impact of CMEs.

When ICMEs travel toward Earth at greater than 90° in Earth's line of sight, CMEs significantly show geo-effectiveness. Magnetic reconnection with Earth's magnetic field is also likely when the leading axial magnetic field is south-directed. Similarly, under the same circumstances, the halo CMEs are responsible for the geomagnetic storms.

A geomagnetic storm usually begins when energy and particles from a CME interact with the Earth's magnetosphere, disrupting the magnetic field. So, determining how

they affect modern technology systems and infrastructure to prepare for and minimize their impact relies on how effective CMEs are in a geographical sense. Predicting when CMEs will arrive and monitoring solar activity enables early action to protect against their harmful effects.

1.3 Corotating Interaction Regions (CIR):

Stream interfaces (SI) were first discovered by Siscoe et al. (1969) as regions characterised by flow shear in the solar wind. Belcher and Davis (1971) did further research, from which a comprehensive view of the boundary separating the slow, cold, and dense solar wind stream from the fast, hot, and tenuous stream emerged. This concept was later named 'Stream Interface' by Burlaga in 1974.

Various investigations have indicated that two separate plasma flows originate from different regions of the solar corona [Gosling et al., 1978; Wimmer-Schweingruber et al., 1999]. SIs are structures of non-continuous shears within the solar wind's flow [Gosling et al., 1978]. Investigating stream interfaces is essential for understanding how plasma stream properties influence solar wind dynamics, as there is a complex interplay of plasma stream properties [Duraïd, 2018].

The solar wind moves at different velocities [Krasnoselskikh et al, 2022]. Generally, the fast solar wind is emitted from coronal holes in the Sun, regions with open magnetic field lines so that charged particles can freely exit them. The slow solar wind emanates from regions of closed solar magnetic field lines [Krasnoselskikh et al, 2022] where magnetic field lines become more confined or interconnected.

As the Sun rotates, these streams of fast and slow solar winds may interact [Krasnoselskikh et al, 2022].

Fig 1.3: Schematic 2D diagram of CIR formation [Pizzo et al., 1999]

The faster solar wind that emits out of coronal holes interacts with the slower solar wind to produce Stream Interaction Regions (SIRs). It can last long, allowing a pattern of recurring corotating fast and slow solar wind flows [Krasnoselskikh et al, 2022] to be observed throughout the heliosphere [Gosling et al., 1999]. This SIR pattern corotates with the Sun during its rotation, and a spiral flow is produced known as the Corotating Interaction Region (CIR) [Duraïd et al., 2018]. Figure 1.3 demonstrates a schematic 2D diagram of the CIR formation [Pizzo et al., 1999].

Heliophysics and space weather involve investigating and predicting the effects of CIRs and ICMEs. CIRs and ICMEs play a significant role in the solar wind [Krasnoselskikh et al, 2022] and their impact on space weather, including geomagnetic storms. As a result, these are important areas for heliophysics research and monitoring. Therefore, CIR is a subclass of SIR structure.

1.4 Geo-effectiveness:

The interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) components (B_x , B_y , and B_z) are important for analysing geomagnetic storms, primarily disturbances within the Earth's magnetosphere driven by the interaction between solar winds and the IMF. This knowledge about their interplay is considered in predicting space weather and minimising its impact on technological systems.

The IMF B_x is oriented along the Sun-Earth direction, and its effect on geomagnetic activity is lower than that of the other components [Krasnoselskikh et al, 2022, Kubyshkina et al., 2023]. However, the IMF B_x orientation can still affect the overall direction of the IMF. The IMF B_y component is perpendicular to the Sun-Earth direction in the ecliptic plane [Kubyshkina et al., 2023]. The azimuthal direction the IMF provides in the plane perpendicular to the Earth-Sun direction influences its interaction with the Earth's magnetosphere.

The essential component of the geomagnetic storm process, the IMF B_z is perpendicular to the ecliptic plane. Represented as a negative value, IMF B_z reflects a southward direction opposite the north-pointing magnetic field of the Earth. Through this direction of magnetic reconnection on the dayside of the magnetosphere, the

magnetosphere can tap energy from the solar wind. One of the most important causes of geomagnetic storms causing great geomagnetic activity, IMF B_z 's southerly trajectory can create disturbance in satellite operation and communication.

Forecasting and reducing the consequences of space weather depend on an awareness of geomagnetic storms and their impact on the ionosphere. Processes of magnetic reconnection explain the importance of IMF B_z in geomagnetic events. Careful monitoring and analysis of these elements, enhanced forecasting and knowledge of system responses to space weather events enable us to protect our technological infrastructure and further our knowledge of solar-terrestrial interactions.

1.5 The Disturbed Storm (Dst) and the K_p index:

The Disturbed Storm (Dst) index, expressed in nano Tesla (nT), is an index for the measurement of the intensity of the geomagnetic storm and the development of the ring current [Moldwin, 2008]. Dst denotes the change in the horizontal component of the earth's geomagnetic field and indicates the magnetic field induced at the ionosphere due to the strength of the ring current in the inner magnetosphere. Dst is measured by averaging the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field from equatorial and mid-latitude magnetograms from the universal setup of magnetometers. So, a negative Dst value indicates a weaker Earth's magnetic field during a geomagnetic storm due to an increase in the strength of the ring current.

Another parameter to study the strength of the geomagnetic storm is the K_p index. The K_p (planetarische Kennziffer) index is a quasi-logarithmic local index of the 3-hour range designed to measure the uneven discrepancies in the Cartesian components of the Earth's magnetic field (X, Y, Z) and is proposed to give a universal measure of geomagnetic activity [Davies, 1990]. First proposed by J. Bartels in 1938, the K_p index is a series of single numbers from 0 to 9, which are assigned for each eight 3-hour universal time (UT) intervals. It is the arithmetic mean of the K values measured at 13 geomagnetic observatories between 48° to 63° degrees North and South geomagnetic latitudes. Therefore, K_p is a geomagnetic index for mid-litudinal geomagnetic index stations. Each observatory has different scales. The maximum value recorded in this range is 500 nT for normal mid-latitude stations and 2000 nT for auroral zone stations.

The K_p index is mainly used for the determination of the amplitude of geomagnetic storms and can be classified as follows: 0-4 is quiet magnetic conditions, 4-6 is moderate magnetic storms and 6-9 is disturbed magnetic conditions [Kivelson and Russell, 1995].

1.6 Technological impacts of geomagnetic storms:

The space environment has a direct impact on spacecraft and astronauts, exposing them to high levels of radiation that can harm or disable systems, cause astronauts to become sick or die, and interfere with radio signals from satellites to the ground for communication and navigation systems like the Global Positioning System (GPS).

Spacecraft surface charging is the result of a reaction between a spacecraft and a low-energy electron environment in the universe. Upon exposure of space satellites to positively and negatively charged particles, no net transfer of charge results in an electrically charged satellite that can produce an electric discharge spark. This can potentially cause damage in the form of overloading of the detectors by intense flashes or the discharge of sensitive electronic components.

Atmospheric drag on Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites and friction force effect can cause the satellite to lose altitude, shifting it to a denser neutral atmosphere. This can heat the satellite so that it will begin to ablate or burn the atmosphere unless it is protected by a strong insulating material. Medium Earth Orbit (MEO), Highly Elliptical Orbit (HEO), and Geo-stationary Earth Orbit (GEO) satellites experience no satellite drag effects. However, they are exposed to doses of high-energy radiation, which can trap their high-energy particles, inflicting severe damage or destruction of sensitive electronic devices.

Intense solar storms can destroy solar cells, essentially shortening the life of satellites. Space weather storms also disrupt radio communication and navigation. Since space weather storms alter the ionosphere density distribution, radio wave propagation depends on the medium. The inhomogeneous ionosphere can greatly disturb and degrade satellite-ground and ground-satellite communication.

Space weather storms can also create High-Frequency (HF) radio blackouts. HF radio propagation depends on the ionospheric density controlled by sunlight and geomagnetic activity. The degradation of HF radio can impact transpolar airline flights. During large geomagnetic storms, HF radio communication can be inoperable over the poles [Moldwin, 2008].

1.7 Lagrangian points:

The Halo orbit is the periodic three-dimensional orbit with a three-body problem of orbital mechanics orbiting near one of the L1, L2, and L3 Lagrangian points. Lagrangian points are peculiar spots in space that can be orbited by a halo or Lissajous orbit under the gravitational force, Coriolis force, and the spacecraft's centrifugal force. Since halo orbits are unstable, station-keeping may be required to keep the satellite in orbit. The L1 point, or the Lagrangian 1 point, illustrated in Fig. 1.5, is the equilibrium position in celestial mechanics for a small mass located near two heavily massive orbiting bodies, where the latter has an unbalanced gravitational effect on the former because of its larger mass. There is a balance between the gravitational effects of the two heavy bodies and the centrifugal force on the small mass at this Lagrangian point. When a third body is located at the Lagrangian points, it is comparatively small and reaches equilibrium with the two directions relative to the centre of

Fig 1.4: Restricted three-body problem [Ghotekar et al., 2019].

Fig 1.5: Halo orbit in L1 position [Courtesy: ESA].

mass of the heavy bodies. The solution of this Lagrangian problem can be solved based on the principles of three-body mechanics.

The L1, L2, and L3 are the positions on the line connecting the centre of mass of the two massive bodies, and L4 and L5 are formed as the third vertex of the equilateral triangle with the centre of mass of the massive bodies, shown in Fig: 1.6. The L1 point lies between the large masses M_1 and M_2 where the equilibrium position is produced due to the combination of the gravitational

Fig 1.6: A counter-plot for generalized potential [Courtesy: Cornish et al, 1998].

attraction between the large bodies. Therefore, it lies exactly equal to the orbital period of the Earth, which is 24 hrs, so that the Earth's gravity counteracts the Sun's pull and the orbital period remains the same. The L2 point lies beyond the smaller of the two large bodies, where the gravitational forces balance the centrifugal force on the body with the orbital period the same as that of the Earth, i.e., about 24 hours. The L3 position lies opposite the sun, a little outside Earth's orbit and slightly close to the sun's centre of mass. The L4 and L5 positions lie on the third corner of the equilateral triangle whose common base is the centre of mass of the two massive bodies.

1.8 Theoretical Framework:

The correlation length is a measurement of the distance between two data points from two satellites that are correlated to one another. It offers a mathematical characterisation of the stochastic dependency of a physical quantity between two points separated by a distance R_E where it remains correlated. The investigation of the correlation coefficient allows one to extract data on solar wind scale lengths, which may also be used to support space weather forecasts using satellite monitors.

Meanwhile, decorrelation length is the statistical limit at which turbulent fluctuations lose coherence. It discloses spatial and temporal scale information to ensure the

correlation remains relevant. Turbulence becomes random at the decorrelation length, the statistical limit scale at which turbulent fluctuations lose their coherence. The decorrelation length reveals when energy transmission and dissipation in turbulence occur.

Recent and past studies have investigated the correlation length of the solar wind magnetic field over short intervals, noting premature drops in the correlation coefficient [Ragot et al., 2022]. Further, researchers have also employed multi-spacecraft measurements to generate correlations from data measured at two points [Wicks et al., 2009; Ragot et al., 2022]. The interplanetary turbulence is analysed at low-frequency plasma based on the two-point, single-time measurements from different spacecraft to get a correlation scale [Dasso et al., 2005]. Furthermore, it has also used satellite data to study the correlation anisotropy of the solar wind at magnetohydrodynamic scales [Gloeckler et al., 1998], paying specific attention to slow solar wind fluctuations [Gloeckler et al., 1998; Dasso et al., 2005].

The spatial structure of transverse oscillations in the interplanetary magnetic field, the coherence region, depends on the scale size of the solar wind velocity [Chang et al., 1972]. The correlation between measurements of the IMF depends on certain factors controlling this correlation [Crooker et al., 1982].

The correlation coefficient can be analysed to extract information on solar wind scale lengths and to aid in forecasting space weather utilising satellite monitors [Richardson et al., 2001]. The decorrelation between IMF fluctuations and distorted turbulent elements has previously been studied [Matthaeus et al., 2010]. Further contributions to understanding the occurrence of oscillations within interplanetary magnetic fields have also been studied previously [Chang et al., 1972].

Previous research has several shortcomings in correlation length analyses; many rely on a single satellite to determine the correlation length, whereas others, such as Wicks et al., 2009 and Ragot et al., 2022, used multiple satellites. In this work, a two-point multi-satellite approach is adopted and using the spatial-temporal windowing technique, correlation length is determined. Also, earlier researchers have not conducted a comparative study of the various categories of solar wind: ICME, CIR, and ambient solar wind, and the spatial inhomogeneity of these categories of solar

wind and its parameters. Therefore, a thorough investigation of the correlation and decorrelation lengths present in these categories is the focus of this work.

The primary objective of this study is to analyse the spatial inhomogeneity of solar wind parameters at the L1 point. By analysing these solar structures' inhomogeneities, it becomes feasible to enhance the precision of predicting the behaviour of the solar wind and consequent impacts on the Earth [Li et al., 2020]. Investigation of the spatial inhomogeneity in solar wind parameters at the L1 halo orbit, such as IMF, density, and velocity is also crucial to understanding the dynamics and organisation of the solar wind. Therefore, the scientific objectives of the work can be stated as follows.

1.9 Objective

- 1 To understand spatial inhomogeneity of solar wind parameters at the halo orbit around the Sun-Earth L1 point and determination of the decorrelation length.
- 2 To study the variation in decorrelation length for different events (ICME, CIR/SIR, and ambient solar wind).
- 3 To find out the connection, if any, between decorrelation length and geo-effectiveness.

Chapter 2:

Dataset and methodology:

The in-situ observations used in this work are derived from various instruments onboard multiple spacecrafts. This chapter details the spacecrafts and their respective instruments.

2.1 The WIND spacecraft:

The WIND spacecraft, part of NASA's Global Geospace Science (GGS) program, is a spin-stabilized spacecraft, launched by NASA in November 1994 at 09:31:00 UT, in the halo orbit of the L1 Lagrange point [Lepping et al, 1995]. The primary objective is to maintain continuous monitoring of the solar wind status at the L1 point and study the solar wind contribution to space weather, the Earth's environment, and the interplanetary medium via measurement of the magnetic field and its contribution to space weather and the Earth's environment. The WIND spacecraft reached its L1 orbit in May 2004 and has enough fuel to operate continuously for more than 50 more years at L1, estimated to continue until at least 2070 [Lepping et al., 1995].

The SWE and MFI are two of several sensors on the WIND satellite that can provide a general overview of solar wind conditions. With the ability to quantify magnetic fields, proton speeds, density, and the alpha-proton ratio, WIND provides science and technology breakthroughs, particularly in solar and terrestrial interaction [NOAA]. Its continued contribution is vital to current and future space missions to comprehend the complexities of our solar environment.

2.1.1 WIND Solar Wind Experiment (SWE):

The WIND spacecraft has a detailed three-dimensional Faraday cup that measures plasma flow in interplanetary space. The main parameters for investigations are velocity, density, and temperature. The spacecraft consists of two Faraday cup (FC)

sensors, a vector electron and ion spectrometer (VEIS), a ‘strahl’ sensor to study the electron “strahl” closed to magnetic field direction, and an onboard calibration system.

WIND uses the Solar Wind Experiment (SWE) to measure the speed of solar wind protons. Using Level-2 accepted data, the SWE instrument analyses characteristics like proton speed and density and provides a comprehensive study of the three-dimensional distribution functions of protons [Elliott et al., 2016]. By inferring such characteristics from protons' velocity distributions, essential information has been obtained about their speed during their journey through space to reach Earth, providing insight into solar winds and space weather.

2.1.2 WIND Magnetic Field Investigation (MFI):

Interplanetary magnetic fields are measured with a dedicated instrument known as the Magnetic Field Investigation (MFI) [Lepping et al., 1995]. The MFI is comprised of two fluxgate magnetometers installed on a 12-m boom. The DC vector fields are measured at a very high sensitivity while the fluctuating time resolution varies between 22 or 11 vectors per second depending on the telemetry mode of operation. It also gives real-time and processed data for studies on the characteristics of the interplanetary magnetic field in detail.

2.2 Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE):

ACE (Advanced Composition Explorer) or Explorer71, a robotic satellite launched on 25 August 1997, entered L1 point on 12 December 1997 [Gloeckler et al., 1998]. It provides advanced knowledge in understanding space weather and solar physics by providing critical data on the interplanetary magnetic field, proton speed and density, and the alpha-proton ratio. The Solar Wind Ion Composition Spectrometer (SWICS) and the Solar Wind Ions Mass Spectrometer (SWIMS) on ACE are instruments optimized for measurements of the chemical and isotopic composition of solar and interstellar matter [Gloeckler et al., 1998]. SWICS uniquely determines the solar wind's chemical and ionic-charge composition and the thermal and mean speeds of all major solar wind ions from H through Fe at all solar wind speeds above 300 km s^{-1}

(protons). ACE enables real-time observation and monitoring of solar wind phenomena, which greatly aids in predicting geomagnetic storms and understanding solar-terrestrial interactions.

SWIMS measures the solar wind's chemical, isotopic, and charge state composition for every element between He and Ni. Each of the two instruments uses electrostatic analysis and a time-of-flight for energy measurement [Gloeckler et al., 1998].

2.2.1 The Magnetic Fields Experiment / Magnetometer (MAG)

ACE monitors interplanetary magnetic fields with its Magnetic Field Experiment or magnetometer (MAG) [Smith et al., 1998]. This experiment uses two vector fluxgate magnetometers that produce extremely sensitive, high-time-resolution measurements of the local magnetic field in the interplanetary medium. Measurements made by MAG are integral for interpreting distributions of energetic and thermal particles and for the dynamics of geomagnetic storms [Smith et al., 1998]. The effectiveness of the design of the MAG instrument has been proved recently by space missions, which detected even the weakest changes in magnetic fields.

2.2.2 The Solar Wind Electron Proton Alpha Monitor (SWEPAM)

The ACE spacecraft uses the Solar Wind Electron Proton Alpha Monitor to obtain the protons' speed within the solar wind. SWEPAM is proton-sensitive at 145 km/s, but sometimes the protons could be highly contaminated because the flux of such protons is large as well as the speeds being slow [McComas et al., 1998; Janet L. Machol et al., 2013]. The SWEPAM-bulk solar wind data can be characterised in greater detail to differentiate between a wide variety of solar wind conditions and extraordinary solar events.

Proton density is also a parameter measured by ACE through the SWEPAM instrument, which measures the solar wind plasma electrons and ions fluxes [Elliott

et al., 2018]. These are important data for researchers involved in computing proton density, given that density varies with changing conditions that occur in the solar wind [King et al., 2005]. Proton density data is useful in assessing the influence of solar winds on Earth's magnetosphere, thereby providing insight into possible effects on geomagnetic activities. The ACE satellite uses the SWEPAM instrument to calculate the solar wind's alpha particle and proton densities [Gloeckler et al., 1998]. The ratio of alpha to proton density is an important ICME indicator [Elliott et al., 2018], which is utilised to provide particle acceleration mechanisms and solar wind output variations caused by solar conditions.

2.3 Data Download and Analysis:

The data for the ACE and WIND satellites were obtained from the website:

<https://cdaweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>. Level 2 data is used in the analysis of both satellites. The MFI instrument on the WIND satellite is used in order to get epoch time, IMF components, proton density, proton velocity, and alpha density. The SWE instrument on the

WIND satellite also provides epoch time and the satellite's position in x, y, and z coordinates in the Geocentric Solar Ecliptic (GSE) system for analysis. WIND satellite data has a cadence of 92 seconds.

Secondly, the MAG instrument on the ACE satellite is utilized to derive the epoch time and IMF components. The SWEPAM instrument on ACE is utilised to get the epoch time, proton density, proton velocity, alpha density, proton density, and satellite position in x, y, and z coordinates in GSE. The cadence of the ACE satellite is 16 seconds. As the cadence of satellite data is not uniform, the data is adjusted to a cadence of 92 seconds to be made homogeneous using Python programming.

Fig 2.1: Positional representation of WIND and ACE spacecraft at L1 point. [Courtesy: NASA]

The following Methodology section provides a detailed description of the data analysis and extraction process.

2.4 Methodology:

A precise space weather forecast relies on the knowledge of the correlation length between the IMF components and the solar wind parameters, measured by multi-satellites. It provides crucial information about the turbulent nature of the solar wind and thus its relevance to forecast space weather accurately. Correlation length can be used to enhance space weather models. These provide insights into solar wind variability's temporal and spatial scales. Multi-satellite missions are used to observe the correlation length to calculate the maximum distance between two spacecrafts in fluctuating magnetic fields that remain correlated [Wicks et al., 2009]. This ensures effective measurement of coherent magnetic field variation and guarantees that the measurements are coherent. Thus, providing the reliability and interpretability of data from multi-spacecraft missions. Hence, correlation length is the key indicator of the spatial extent over which the magnetic field fluctuations are interrelated. Therefore, accurate solar wind and IMF models rely on the knowledge of the correlation length to simulate realistic magnetic field structures for improved space weather forecasts.

The correlation length provides information about the physics governing solar wind dynamics. Such measurement of spatial correlation of the magnetic fluctuations, driven by the turbulence beginning from the corona, provides insights into how those processes interact and evolve. The correlation length measures spatial correlation in magnetic field fluctuations and is a key tool to improve our knowledge of solar wind dynamics and make better space weather forecasts. This can be quantified using multi-satellite in-situ measurements of how the solar wind activity impacts the Earth's magnetosphere. It is also determined by calculating the correlation length (λ_c) and determining how the fluctuations in the solar wind flow correlate in space and time. This allows one to interpret solar wind properties [Wicks et al., 2009].

A comprehensive analysis of Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections (ICMEs), Stream Interaction Regions (SIR/CIR), and ambient solar wind events is conducted for solar cycle 24, from 2009 to 2019. The data is collected from ACE and WIND, with a data cadence of 16 seconds, and 92-second respectively. The satellite's data are then

converted to a cadence of 92 seconds. The parameters considered for the solar events are the IMF components B_x (nT), B_y (nT), and B_z (nT), solar wind proton density (cm^{-3}), proton speed (km/s), and alpha proton density ratio ($n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}}$). The alpha proton density ratio is expressed as $n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}} = (N_{\text{a}}/N_{\text{p}}) * 100$; where N_{a} is the He density, and N_{p} is the proton density [Yogesh et al., 2023].

For these studies, the ICMEs have been collected from the ICME catalogue [Richardson and Cane 2010] and the CIR/SIR list [Chi et al., 2018]. The SIR catalogue is available for the years 1998–2016. The data is collected from the GSFC CDA Web (URL: SPDF—Coordinated Data Analysis Web (CDA Web) (nasa.gov)) for the satellites ACE and WIND. The ambient solar wind is assessed bi-monthly, excluding SIR and ICME event data.

2.4.1 Data Calibration:

Simultaneous observations from the ACE and WIND spacecraft are used to compute the linear correlation coefficient of plasma parameters (e.g., interplanetary magnetic field components, proton density, etc) as a function of spacecraft separation. However, data gaps are an unavoidable feature of satellite datasets, and may arise from instrument issues, telemetry errors, or scheduled calibration and maintenance activities. ACE provides measurements at a 16-second cadence, whereas WIND data is available at a 92-second cadence. To analyse the data in a uniform manner and enable meaningful comparison a joint analysis is made to resample the higher-resolution ACE data to match the lower-resolution WIND cadence. This ensures that both datasets can be compared or used together without introducing temporal bias. The alignment was done using the Python programming, which aligns the ACE data to the WIND data points systematically by averaging over a symmetric time window. WIND data is used as the reference timeline and computed appropriately with ACE values at each WIND timestamp due to its coarser (92-second) cadence. For each timestamp in the WIND dataset, a time window of ± 46 seconds is defined, resulting in a total window size of 92 seconds. Within this window, the function selects all ACE data points whose timestamps fall within the range. If data points are within the

window, their average is calculated along the respective axis. To maintain shape consistency, an empty array filled with NaN (Not-a-Number) is created if no data points are identified, which could occur due to gaps in the data. This average value is added to the output array, which finally holds the ACE data converted to the WIND cadence. This average serves as the representative ACE value that is associated with that particular WIND timestamp. This approach preserves the integrity of the comparison between the two datasets while statistically significantly down-sampling the higher-frequency ACE data.

2.5 Estimation of correlation length (λ_c):

The correlation length measures the distance between two data points from the two satellites over which a physical quantity remains correlated. The correlation length between the ACE and WIND satellites is calculated using linear cross-correlation. This analysis specifically measures the correlation between the two signals for parameters such as IMF B_x , B_y , and B_z , proton density, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio (n_{He}/n_H) during the solar events SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind.

The Pearson cross-correlation is analysed from the formula:

$$C(A, B) = \frac{E[(A - \bar{A}) \cdot (B - \bar{B})]}{E[(A - \bar{A})^2] \cdot E[(B - \bar{B})^2]} \quad (2.1)$$

Then a spatial variation of the linear correlation coefficient on the exponential form with a fit of

$$y(C) = a \exp\left(-\frac{S}{\lambda_c}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

Where S is the separation between the satellites and ‘ a ’ is presumed as 1 to see the dependence of correlation coefficient, $y(C)$, over the average separation between the satellites S ; and λ_c is the correlation length [Wicks et al, 2009]. The correlation length is estimated from individual linear correlation coefficients and the correlation length (λ_c) is given by

$$C = e^{-\frac{S}{\lambda_c}} \quad \text{—————} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\lambda_c = \frac{-S}{\ln(C)} \quad \text{—————} \quad (2.4)$$

λ_c is the estimated correlation length, S is the average separation length between the satellites, and C is the correlation coefficient [Wicks et al, 2009]. After integrating the equation into the dataset, an exponential curve-fitting model is applied to determine the correlation length from the fit across the entire dataset of events.

Euclidean distance is the distance between any two points in space and could be defined as the square root of the sum of the squares of the two spacecraft from each point's differences. The Euclidean distance 'd' between two points (x_1, y_1, z_1) and (x_2, y_2, z_2) of the spacecraft is given by:

$$d = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2 + (z_1 - z_2)^2} \quad \text{—————} \quad (2.5)$$

The nonlinear least-squares fit of the R^2 is utilised to determine the strength of the correlation length between the model and the fitted value. The equation for the R^2 value given for the fit as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - f_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad \text{—————} \quad (2.6)$$

Where f_i is the fit, y_i is the data and \bar{y} is the mean of the data. The characteristic R^2 value indicates the effectiveness of the fit in elucidating the data's variation, with 1 signifying a perfect fit and 0 indicating a poor fit [Wicks et al, 2009].

The decorrelation length is computed by establishing the amount of separation at which correlation decays to a specific fraction (f) of its value. Decorrelation occurs for exponential decay models at a value equivalent to $1/e$ (~ 0.3679) of its original value, which is taken as an ideal threshold for theoretical analysis. However, in practical applications, λ_d may be set to reflect different correlation thresholds (e.g., $f = 0.5$ or $f = 0.1$), depending on physical context or modelling needs. Therefore, it can imply that the decorrelation length is the statistical limit that indicates the turbulent fluctuations no longer exhibit coherence after a certain length. It reveals spatial and temporal scale information so that the correlation remains relevant.

The equation to determine the decorrelation is given by

$$R(\Delta\lambda_d) = f \cdot R(0)$$

$$e^{-\frac{\lambda_d}{\lambda_c}} = f$$

$$-\frac{\lambda_d}{\lambda_c} = \ln(f)$$

$$\lambda_d = \lambda_c \ln(f)$$

$$\lambda_d = \lambda_c \ln\left(\frac{1}{e}\right)$$

$$\lambda_d = 0.999 \lambda_c \quad \text{—————} \quad (2.7)$$

This study aims to observe the correlation length and the decorrelation length for the different solar events i.e., for ICME, CIR/SIR and ambient solar wind. The correlation length gives the spatial scale over which the physical quantities e.g., the magnetic field, plasma velocity etc., remain statistically correlated. It mathematically defines

the statistical dependence of a physical quantity between two points separated by a distance R_E where it remains correlated.

Contrary to this, the decorrelation length is defined as the statistical limit scale over which the turbulent fluctuations lose their coherence, implying the scale where turbulence

Fig 2.2: Variations of various parameters of the satellites ACE (solid orange line) and WIND (solid blue line) i.e., IMF B_x , IMF B_y and IMF B_z , Proton Density (N_p) and Proton Speed (V_p) and the average distance between the satellites in R_E (solid green line), for a ICME event on 15th to 27th April 2014.

transitions from being coherent to random. So, the decorrelation length analyses the point after which energy transfer and dissipation in turbulence occur.

The Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection (ICME) and Stream Interaction Regions (SIR) events are taken from the abovementioned events catalogue. From the GSFC CDA NASA website, the data is collected from the ACE and WIND satellites for the considered parameters, an example shown in Fig: 2.2 for an ICME event from 15th to 27th April 2014 along with the average distance between the satellites in R_E . Then, for each chosen solar event, a synthetic time window of a specific time interval, explained later in sections 2.5.1 and 2.5.2, within the ICME and SIR, and corresponding ambient solar wind is created for the same duration. To ensure analysis homogeneity, assume an equal number of ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind for the year. The correlation coefficient for each solar event and its parameters was determined using the data points gathered annually at a 92-second cadence.

After computing the correlation coefficients for all solar events and their parameters, the correlation length, the decorrelation length, and the R^2 value for the entire year are analysed and discussed in Chapter -3. The equations from 2.1 to 2.7 have been applied here to investigate the correlation length of ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind conditions. This has been expanded upon for various solar phases within the solar cycle discussed in Chapter-4, to provide a thorough investigation of space weather.

The correlation and the decorrelation length for each year for the whole solar cycle 24, i.e., 2009-2019, are analysed. A comprehensive study is also done on the variation of the correlation length and the decorrelation length for solar cycle 24, solar maximum and solar minimum, and the ascending and descending phases of solar cycle 24.

2.5.1 Determination of optical temporal window for the analysis of Correlation/Decorrelation lengths:

Least squares fit is applied to study the correlation data for each parameter between ICME, SIR, and the ambient solar wind. The solar wind composition displays a wide range of spatial and temporal scales, from large-scale variations to small-scale variations. This can introduce an estimate of the error in the correlation length.

Large-scale characteristics, such as CMEs, are important. Still, interaction regions, such as Corotating Interaction regions (CIRs), and ambient wind flow patterns are also important in shaping or arranging large volumes of interplanetary plasma [Matthaus, 1986]. To calculate the cross-correlation from the dataset, it is essential to establish a window length, denoted as τ .

The fast Fourier transformation (FFT) method is used to construct a power spectral density (PSD) from the magnetic field time series by creating an artificial time series that contains information about the magnetic field changes across the strong solar wind current sheets [Borovsky et al., 2020]. A synthetic time window is generated, and then the PSD is obtained using FFT. After that, the PSD is plotted against frequency, and the slope in terms of spectral power characteristics is interpreted.

The windowing technique enables a more detailed analysis of the solar wind, giving a deeper insight into its magnetic power spectra.

The Fast Fourier Transform of a sequence $x[n]$ is defined by the following equation for calculating the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT):

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] \cdot e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{N}kn}, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1 \quad \text{———— (2.8)}$$

The equation converts the Fourier coefficients $X[k]$ into the sum of time domain samples $x[n]$, N is the total number of points in the sequence and k is the index of the frequency components, with $e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{N}kn}$, being the complex exponential expression for basic functions of the DFT.

The Power Spectral Density is stated in terms of the Fourier transform of the signal. The normalised power spectral density spectrum is given by:

$$PSD(f) = \frac{1}{N} |X[k]|^2, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1 \quad \text{—————} \quad (2.9)$$

In this expression, the squared magnitude $|X[k]|^2$ represents the power corresponding to each frequency bin, normalised by the number of samples N to produce the normalised outcome.

The spectral index, α in a power-law equation, where the power spectral density $P(f)$ is proportional to the inverse of frequency, f raised to the power of α , which reflects the rate at which power decreases with increasing frequency [Goldstein et al, 1995].

$$P(f) \propto f^{-\alpha} \quad \text{—————} \quad (2.10)$$

Specifically, the Kolmogorov turbulence is assumed to have a slope of $-5/3$ in the power-law relation for the higher frequency [Goldstein et al., 1995]. While calculating the slope, a synthetic time series is extracted, and the value is estimated. If the slope value does not match, the time series length is iterated to another synthetic time series length to acquire a log-log plot whose slope is equivalent to the expected Kolmogorov value. The optimal time series length is the time window that aligns with the Kolmogorov slope.

The spectral slopes represented in Fig. 2.3 are α_{mid} , α_{MHD} , and the power law spectrum $\alpha(f)$, which are all essential to understanding the process of turbulence in the solar wind [Borovsky et al., 2020].

This study's analysis aims to understand how solar wind will affect space weather, the heliosphere, and basic plasma physics. Therefore, analysing the spectral slopes of solar wind's PSD will provide insights into the physics of plasma [Borovsky et al., 2020] interaction in space weather.

2.5.2 Spectral Scaling of Solar Wind:

In Fig. 2.3, the time windowing is found by using the equations from 2.8 to 2.10 for the ambient solar wind, considered as the background solar wind, for 16th August 2024, from 00:00:30 hrs to 16:00:42 hrs, where α_{mid} coincides with the Kolmogorov slope of $-5/3$.

α_{mid} : α_{mid} , which is the inertial range, is the gradient slope designating the initial turbulence range and transition range when power cascades from layers into smaller scales without dissipation.

Understanding how energy transfers in the solar wind is very crucial [Goldstein et al., 1995; Borovsky et al., 2015].

$\alpha(f)$: A global power spectrum $\alpha(f)$ supplies an integrated view of how PSD varies with frequency across all turbulence regimes. Understanding the slope in that range helps identify the nature of energy input into solar wind turbulence.

Inertial Range (α_{mid}): For MHD turbulence, the slope has to be between Kolmogorov turbulence, $\alpha = -5/3$, or about $\alpha = -3/2$ as in the Iroshnikov-Kraichnan slope, which signifies that there exists a cascade process typical of MHD turbulence [Goldstein et al., 1995; Borovsky et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2023]. Solar wind turbulence is energy transferring from large scales to smaller scales. The inertial range is defined by α_{mid} . α_{mid} is important for understanding this energy transfer mechanism [Goldstein et al., 1995; Borovsky et al., 2020].

Fig 2.3: Windowing technique to find the time window

High-Frequency Range (Dissipation Range, α_{MHD}): The α_{MHD} slope here reflects kinetic processes and wave-particle interaction. Spectral slopes in the high-frequency range, α_{MHD} , indicate a possible interaction of particles with kinetic Alfvén or another type of plasma wave [Huang et al., 2023].

To get a holistic understanding of the turbulent dynamics in the solar wind, the calculation of the spectral slopes α_{mid} , α_{MHD} , and (f) is required [Borovsky et al., 2020]. Calculations that improve the validation of theoretical models provide more insight into energy transfer mechanisms in effect. The accuracy of forecasts of space weather could also be enhanced. For a greater understanding of heliophysical and astrophysical turbulence, these techniques and analyses applied in the calculations are essential.

FFT is standard in solar wind turbulence studies, especially to confirm the inertial range. In Fig 2.3 the FFT, sm FFT and WL represents Fast Fourier Transformation, smooth Fast Fourier Transformation and Welch’s Method respectively. This method is used to compute the power spectral density (PSD) of magnetic field fluctuations in the solar wind. FFT is commonly used for its computational efficiency and high-resolution insight, particularly in identifying sharp spectral breaks or resolving narrowband structures. It forms the baseline spectrum in the plot. Computing the PSD via FFT is the standard way to diagnose turbulence: it reveals broad power-law ranges that reflect the underlying cascade of energy across scales. FFT-based spectra are essential for identifying this turbulence scaling laws and comparing with MHD turbulence theories.

The FFT periodogram is often quite noisy at high frequencies, due to finite data and statistical fluctuations. There is a common practice of smoothing the FFT spectrum in order to facilitate the visual identification of power-law regions as well as to make slope estimation more stable and consistent with the statistical interpretation of power-law behaviour. Despite the smoothed FFT represents the same PSD, the scatter has been reduced, allowing a better understanding of broad trends.

Welch's method computes the PSD by dividing the time series into overlapping segments, applying a Hanning window, and then averaging the periodograms. Mathematically, this averages the random variations in each segment’s spectrum, “averaging out” the fluctuations due to noise. This is how different segments of the scaling spectrum can be derived.

2.5.3 Optimal Time Window selection for Solar wind analysis:

The time window, τ , is the time ensemble over which we compute the expected values of the signals. An ensemble for the specific time window is generated using the equations from 2.8 to 2.10 and plotted in Fig. 2.3. The time window focuses on the solar wind's large-scale structure to optimise for the timeframes observed in the power spectrum. As shown in Figure 2.3, the aforementioned approach is used to construct an optimum time window that coincides with the Kolmogorov frequency (α_{mid}).

To determine the optimal time window a synthetic time series is extracted from the ambient solar wind, which is considered as the background solar wind, and computed using the equations mentioned above and a figure, like Fig: 2.3, is plotted and analysed to see if α_{mid} matches with the Kolmogorov slope. If the synthetic time series does not synchronise with the Kolmogorov slope the time series is iterated again and analysed. Based on trial-and-error testing, 960 minutes is found to be the optimal time window, which matches the Kolmogorov slope i.e., α_{mid} equals $-5/3$.

The time window is then systematically shifted through the dataset one step at a time [Wicks et al., 2009]. The ICME and SIR events are chosen from the event catalogue. The time window is taken from within the ICME and SIR and associated ambient solar wind events for every chosen event. An equal amount of ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind events are taken into account every year to maintain the homogeneity of analysis. During the correlation analysis, any instances where either ACE or WIND data contains NaN values are automatically excluded from the computation of the linear correlation coefficient using the numpy or pandas of Python programming during correlation functions, which ignore NaN by default.

Since the analysis is performed within 16-hour non-overlapping windows, which corresponds to the inertial range i.e., Kolmogorov time window, ensures that the statistical properties of the data, including the correlation coefficient, are computed only over intervals sufficiently long to contain meaningful variability but short enough to maintain consistency. If a data gap within a 16-hour window leads to missing data for either ACE or WIND at a particular timestamp, the corresponding entry is treated

as NaN. However, as long as the majority of the data within the 16-hour window is present, the correlation coefficient is calculated first by excluding the points that correlate to the NaN. If large gaps dominate the window (e.g., multiple consecutive missing values spanning a significant fraction of the window), that window is flagged and excluded from the statistical analysis. This approach is consistent with standard practices in time-series analysis of space plasma data and ensures the robustness and reliability of the reported correlation results.

Applying the time window, the correlation length for each solar event and parameters are compared and analysed for each year for the entire solar cycle 24. Comparative studies are analysed on the correlation length for the solar maximum and solar minimum for each solar event and its parameters. Similarly, comparative studies of the correlation length for each solar event and its parameters are analysed for the ascending and descending solar cycle phases.

The correlation coefficient of the two satellites with the 92-second cadence, in the ensemble of 960-minute time windows, is calculated for all solar events and parameters using Equation 2.1. Once the correlation coefficient for all the solar events and parameters is determined, the correlation length is verified by equation 2.4 for each year of solar cycle 24. This process is intended to examine a relative comparison of solar events ICME, SIR, and the ambient solar wind conditions. It thus contributes to a detailed investigation of the space weather events of the selected duration. The decorrelation length by equation 2.7 for the entire year and the R^2 value by equation 2.6 are then calculated.

Chapter 3:

Variation in decorrelation lengths during ICME and SIR events in solar cycle 24:

Space weather, referring to the Sun and the solar wind conditions, studies the impact of the solar-terrestrial relationship. The solar wind, a natural plasma environment, offers an ideal environment for understanding and investigating plasma turbulence in magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) scales. The studies in this chapter are performed by using multi-spacecraft data. This analysis will unveil a detailed exploration of solar wind fluctuation that can detect spatial features. This includes simultaneous satellite data measurement at two distinct points within the same timeframe that helps map the spatial structure. This multi-satellite technique using a flotilla of spacecraft helps to examine the conditions in the heliosphere and conduct in-depth multipoint data studies [Matthaeus et al., 2005]. The advanced spatiotemporal method is estimated using the windowing methodology explained in Chapter 2 of the methodology section, for the spatial correlation function and correlation length scales. This technique helps to enhance our understanding of the many spatial scales at which plasma turbulence manifests within the heliospheric environment.

The correlation length indicates how long-range interactions can persist within turbulence. A reduced correlation length signifies heightened turbulence dissipation [Matthaeus et al., 2005], while an extended correlation length implies greater coherence in plasma structures. ICMEs and SIRs interact distinctly from the ambient solar wind. One can determine how transient vs. recurrent patterns evolve during periods of weak solar activity by using their respective correlation lengths across the cycle. Whereas decorrelation length is the statistical distance or time scale across which turbulent fluctuations lose coherence, therefore revealing the spatial and temporal extent up to which correlations remain significant.

In comparison to prior cycles, solar cycle 24 is among the weakest in over a century, has significantly diminished sunspot numbers, decreased solar wind pressure, and reduced interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) intensity [Gopalswamy et al., 2015]. This

is a unique opportunity to examine the impact of reduced solar activity on the structure and evolution of turbulence within the heliosphere. These elements render investigating the effect of reduced solar activity scientifically captivating. Weak solar wind conditions can change turbulence features, influencing magnetohydrodynamic cascade processes [Bruno & Carbone, 2013]. Investigating these features improves theoretical models of turbulent flow inside the heliosphere. Solar Cycle 24 had less intense ICMEs compared to previous cycles, although it has increased slow wind-driven SIRs.

Also, the Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) and WIND satellites provide concurrent studies of solar wind properties at many heliospheric locations. Launched in August 1997, ACE entered the L1 point on December 12, 1997, and has generated high-quality solar wind data; WIND, which entered at the L1 point in May 2004, offers complementary plasma observations. Operating during the entire cycle, ACE and WIND generated continuous, high-resolution multi-point solar wind observations, thereby facilitating a robust estimation of spatial correlation scales.

In this chapter, the power spectrum data is analysed using the windowing technique and the time series is aligned with the $-5/3$ Kolmogorov slope, i.e., 960 minutes, as described in Chapter -2. 960 minutes of data from every event is extracted for analysis. Then the correlation coefficient is computed and shifted forward by the sliding window technique over the whole event to determine the correlation coefficient. Then the correlation length (λ_c) for every year over the entire solar cycle 24 is computed. The results, including the R^2 values, are discussed in detail. Correlation and decorrelation lengths are analysed and compared for each solar cycle's year for various solar wind categories and then tabulated. An annual study reveals the impact of heliospheric conditions on local turbulence parameters, thus distinguishing the global predictable trends in solar wind turbulence development. A comparative analysis of every event is investigated, and observations are noted below.

3.1 RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS:

In a comparative analysis of correlation lengths for ambient solar wind, stream interaction regions (SIRs) or corotating interaction regions (CIRs), and interplanetary coronal mass ejections (ICMEs), it has been observed that the ambient solar wind exhibited the shortest correlation length comparatively to SIR and ICME. Ambient solar wind can be referred to as the background solar wind. ICME has the highest correlation length while SIR/CIR events have an intermediate correlation length.

During 2009, the commencement of solar cycle 24 signalled the onset of a record decrease in solar activity, with a mean annual sunspot number of 4.8 [WDC-SILSO, Royal Observatory of Belgium, Brussels]. Only 10 out of 11 ICME events were available for analysis. The details collected from the ICME catalogue reveal that the solar wind speed maximum corresponding to the ICME was 450 km/s and the maximum strength of the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) observed was 12 nT [Richardson and Cane 2010]. This finding reveals a comparatively lower level of turbulence in ICMEs. The number of SIR/CIR events identified from the CIR/SIR catalogue was 42 [Chi et al., 2018]. This finding reveals that the SIR occurrence of SIRs was comparatively more frequent than ICMEs in the corresponding year and hence impacted solar wind turbulence. Investigating the correlation length of this year serves as a critical baseline for understanding turbulence evolution in weak solar conditions.

Table 3.1 compares the correlation length, including positive and negative errors, decorrelation length, and R^2 values for ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind for the year 2009.

Table - 3.1: Decorrelation lengths for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2009

2009	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$117.64^{+8.95}_{-10.5}$	117.529	0.495	$227.27^{+42.0}_{-66.8}$	227.045	0.075	$69.93^{+4.1}_{-4.6}$	69.860	0.275
B_y	$135.13^{+10.13}_{-11.92}$	135	0.255	$357.14^{+71.4}_{-119.0}$	356.785	0.104	$102.04^{+5.8}_{-6.6}$	101.938	0.215
B_z	$114.94^{+9.6}_{-11.63}$	114.827	0.538	$232.55^{+53.9}_{-100.7}$	232.325	0.063	$72.99^{+4.4}_{-5.1}$	72.919	0.226
Proton Density	$144.92^{+15.05}_{-19.0}$	144.782	0.268	$200.00^{+48.4}_{-94.1}$	199.8	0.022	$107.52^{+8.5}_{-10.1}$	107.419	0.289
Proton Speed	$270.27^{+32.17}_{-42.22}$	270	0.107	$384.61^{+62.0}_{-91.5}$	384.230	0.184	$172.41^{+16.1}_{-19.8}$	172.241	0.069
Alpha Proton Density	$89.28^{+9.92}_{-12.75}$	89.196	0.151	$111.11^{+26.3}_{-50.1}$	111	0.051	$82.64^{+6.3}_{-7.4}$	82.561	0.160

In 2009 as tabulated in Table 3.1, satellite separations ranged from 35 Earth radii (R_E) to 140 R_E , and across all components of the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF), the ordering for correlation length was found to be $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{SIR} > \lambda_{Amb}$. For proton density, $\lambda_{ICME}(N_p) > \lambda_{SIR}(N_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(N_p)$, and for proton speed $\lambda_{ICME}(V_p) > \lambda_{SIR}(V_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(V_p)$. Additionally for alpha proton density ratio $\lambda_{ICME}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{SIR}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb}(n_{He}/n_H)$. In 2009, marking the beginning of solar cycle 24, it was observed that the correlation length of ICMEs for the IMF B_y component was significantly higher than in earlier studies, specifically extending to 356.785 R_E , with an error of +71.4 R_E and -119 R_E , surpassing the previously observed correlation length of 300 R_E [Matthaeus et al., 2005]. The observed disparity may have stemmed from 2009 being a relatively quiet year with few ICME events. This lack of ICME events could be the underlying cause of the observed disparity. It has been observed that the R^2 value is consistently below 0.5 for all events due to the same disparity mentioned above for 2009 and also largely due to measurement scatter caused by the highly variable nature of the solar wind.

For 2010, the average annual sunspot count was 24.9, with 15 ICMEs. This signifies a progressive rise, nevertheless remaining relatively weak. The maximum intensity of the interplanetary magnetic field has been estimated to be 14 nT, while the peak velocity of the solar wind approached 790 km/s. A total of 42 SIR/CIR incidents occurred the majority of which led to turbulent conditions. The results of the correlation length comparison from 2010 are displayed in Table 3.2. The results encompass positive and negative errors, decorrelation length and R^2 values for ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind phenomena.

Table – 3.2: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2010

2010	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$87.71^{+6.4}_{-7.5}$	87.631	0.286	$109.89^{+17.2}_{-25.2}$	109.780	0.171	$94.33^{+8.1}_{-9.8}$	94.245	0.276
B_y	$54.05^{+4.0}_{-4.7}$	54	0.193	$95.23^{+13.2}_{-18.3}$	95.142	0.140	$64.51^{+6.0}_{-7.4}$	64.451	0.318
B_z	$97.08^{+7.8}_{-9.2}$	96.990	0.297	$96.15^{+14.8}_{-21.4}$	96.057	0.325	$79.36^{+6.3}_{-7.5}$	79.285	0.370
Proton Density	$94.33^{+11.6}_{-15.5}$	94.245	0.205	$50.25^{+10.5}_{-18.0}$	50.201	0.152	$76.33^{+6.4}_{-7.6}$	76.259	0.150
Proton Speed	$227.27^{+23.8}_{-29.1}$	227.045	0.050	$243.90^{+58.7}_{-90.0}$	243.658	0.275	$163.93^{+16.8}_{-21.2}$	163.770	0.125
Alpha Proton Density	$76.92^{+11.1}_{-15.6}$	76.846	0.249	$72.99^{+20.9}_{-48.9}$	72.919	0.165	$49.75^{+4.7}_{-5.8}$	49.701	0.504

In 2010 as tabulated in Table 3.2, satellite separations ranged from 41 R_E to 230 R_E for the entire year, the correlation length for the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) varies across different components: along IMF B_x is $\lambda_{ICME}(B_x) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_x) > \lambda_{SIR}(B_x)$, along IMF B_y is $\lambda_{ICME}(B_y) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_y) > \lambda_{SIR}(B_y)$, along IMF B_z , is $\lambda_{SIR}(B_z) > \lambda_{ICME}(B_z) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_z)$, Proton density exhibits a different pattern: $\lambda_{SIR}(N_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(N_p) > \lambda_{ICME}(N_p)$. Similarly, for proton speed $\lambda_{ICME}(V_p) > \lambda_{SIR}(V_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(V_p)$, Additionally, the alpha proton density ratio follows the trend: $\lambda_{SIR}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{ICME}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb}(n_{He}/n_H)$. In the case of IMF B_x and IMF B_y , the ambient solar wind correlation length is slightly larger than that of SIR. The discrepancy results from the higher homogeneity and less turbulence of the ambient solar wind, which on more prolonged periods has a more consistent magnetic field. On the other hand, the compressive and turbulent interactions within SIRs produce more turbulence and unpredictability that reduces correlation lengths [Richardson, 2018]. SIR correlation length for the alpha proton density ratio and IMF B_z is substantially comparable but slightly greater than in ICMEs. This can be explained by both SIRs' and ICMEs' similar chaotic nature. The discrepancy in proton density results from the lack of ICME events to measure it, which causes the correlation length in ICMEs to be far smaller. Proton speed follows a known pattern: the correlation length in ICMEs is longer than in SIRs and the correlation length in SIRs is longer than in ambient solar wind. The exceedingly turbulent character of the solar wind causes measurement scatter that results in an R^2 value less than 0.5.

The total average number of sunspots for the year 2011 was 80.8, and there were a total of 32 ICME occurrences. A maximum solar wind speed of 700 km/s and an IMF strength of 21 nT, indicate a gradual increase in solar wind disturbances. 42 SIR/CIR incidents have been recorded. This year shows an almost equal number of both the events i.e., ICME and SIR-driven turbulence coexisted, influencing correlation lengths differently than in the minimum years. Table 3.3 has been updated to include the findings of the correlation length comparison conducted in 2011. The findings include positive and negative errors, values for decorrelation length and R^2 for ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind events.

Table – 3.3: Decorrelation lengths for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2011

2011	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$93.45^{+7.2}_{-8.5}$	93.364	0.281	$135.13^{+16.0}_{-21.1}$	135	0.564	$65.78^{+4.8}_{-5.6}$	65.723	0.037
B_y	$101.01^{+8.4}_{-10.10}$	100.909	0.290	$136.98^{+17.9}_{-24.3}$	136.849	0.109	$87.71^{+6.4}_{-7.5}$	87.631	0.354
B_z	$81.30^{+6.6}_{-7.9}$	81.219	0.176	$128.20^{+17.0}_{-23.3}$	128.076	0.126	$60.97^{+3.8}_{-4.3}$	60.914	0.287
Proton Density	$153.84^{+23.9}_{-34.8}$	153.692	0.160	$98.03^{+16.0}_{-23.9}$	97.941	0.094	$96.15^{+8.4}_{-10.2}$	96.057	0.287
Proton Speed	$243.90^{+21.6}_{-26.3}$	243.658	0.330	$232.55^{+32.5}_{-45.2}$	232.325	0.327	$126.58^{+12.9}_{-16.2}$	126.455	0.235
Alpha Proton Density	$73.52^{+9.8}_{-13.4}$	73.455	0.253	$91.74^{+14.8}_{-21.8}$	91.651	0.349	$85.47^{+8.5}_{-10.6}$	85.384	0.276

In 2011 as tabulated in Table 3.3, satellite separations ranged from 44 R_E to 145 R_E for the entire year, and the correlation lengths for the IMF components exhibit the order $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{SIR} > \lambda_{amb}$, for proton density, the order is reversed: $\lambda_{SIR} (N_p) > \lambda_{ICME}(N_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (N_p)$, Similarly, for proton speed, $\lambda_{SIR} (V_p) > \lambda_{ICME} (V_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (V_p)$, Furthermore, concerning the alpha proton density ratio, $\lambda_{ICME} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{SIR} (n_{He}/n_H)$. In the proton density and proton velocity measurement, SIRs' correlation length is larger than that of ICMEs. ICME and ambient solar wind, have nearly identical correlation lengths. SIRs' higher correlation length as compared to ICMEs can be explained by the disturbed and interaction-rich fields of SIRs, which are characterised by high variability and turbulence [Richardson, 2018]. For the alpha-protons density ratio, the ICME's correlation length is longer than in ambient solar wind and longer compared to SIR. The value of R^2 is determined as less than 0.35 suggesting the fitness to be inadmissible, this is due to the strong variability and chaotic nature of solar wind [Taylor et al., 1996].

The average monthly sunspot number in 2012 was 84.5; the maximum solar wind speed was 890 km/s; the IMF was 28 nT; and 33 SIR/CIR events with roughly equal numbers of both. The solar maximum phase started this year accompanied by significant solar activity, active solar wind structures and increasing degrees of turbulence. Table 3.4 illustrates the comparative analysis of ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind correlation lengths, including positive and negative errors, decorrelation lengths, and R^2 values.

Table – 3.4: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2012

2012	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$101.01^{+9.2}_{-11.3}$	100.909	0.363	$125.0^{+11.3}_{-13.8}$	124.875	0.279	$87.71^{+7.0}_{-8.4}$	87.631	0.118
B_y	$138.88^{+13.8}_{-17.3}$	138.75	0.322	$217.39^{+25.0}_{-32.6}$	217.173	0.129	$123.45^{+9.8}_{-11.6}$	123.333	0.260
B_z	$108.69^{+9.6}_{-11.7}$	108.587	0.095	$169.49^{+17.9}_{-22.8}$	169.322	0.348	$109.89^{+7.8}_{-9.1}$	109.780	0.291
Proton Density	$86.95^{+15.0}_{-22.9}$	86.869	0.380	$84.03^{+14.5}_{-22.3}$	83.949	0.258	$80^{+7.0}_{-8.4}$	79.920	0.105
Proton Speed	$270.27^{+37.7}_{-52.3}$	270	0.357	$217.39^{+28.7}_{-39.0}$	217.173	0.456	$172^{+16.1}_{-19.8}$	172.241	0.150
Alpha Proton Density	$91.74^{+15.4}_{-23.1}$	91.651	0.384	$70.42^{+10.8}_{-15.7}$	70.352	0.011	$64.51^{+4.6}_{-5.4}$	64.451	0.300

In 2012 as detailed in Table 3.4, satellite separations varied from 45 R_E to 220 R_E for the entire year, the correlation lengths for the IMF components follow these patterns: along IMF B_x , $\lambda_{ICME}(B_x) > \lambda_{SIR}(B_x) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_x)$, for IMF along B_y is $\lambda_{ICME}(B_y) > \lambda_{SIR}(B_y) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_y)$, for IMF along B_z is $\lambda_{ICME}(B_z) > \lambda_{SIR}(B_z) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_z)$, for proton density $\lambda_{SIR}(N_p) > \lambda_{ICME}(N_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(N_p)$, for proton speed $\lambda_{SIR}(V_p) > \lambda_{ICME}(V_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(V_p)$, furthermore for alpha proton density ratio $\lambda_{SIR}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{ICME}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb}(n_{He}/n_H)$. For all components of the IMF, the correlation length for ICMEs is greater than that for SIRs, which in turn is greater than that for the ambient solar wind. However, for proton density, proton speed, and the alpha proton density ratio, the correlation length for SIRs exceeds that of ICMEs, which is higher than that of the ambient solar wind, due to SIR interactions' turbulent and compressive nature. The R^2 value is found to be below 0.45. The correlation length versus the separation between the two satellites' plots for the different parameters for ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind events are shown in Fig: 3.1 to Fig: 3.6 where the correlation is shown in blue scattered dots, and the red line is fit to find the correlation length.

Fig 3.1: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_x for the year 2012 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.2: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_y for the year 2012 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.3: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_z for the year 2012 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.4: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for proton density for the year 2012 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.5: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for proton speed for the year 2012 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.6: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for alpha proton density ratio for the year 2012 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

A study conducted in 2013 investigates the correlation length, including both positive and negative errors, as well as the decorrelation length and the R^2 value. This year corresponds to the peak years of solar cycle 24, characterized by a maximum in solar activity with an average sunspot number of 94 alongside 25 ICME events with maximum solar wind velocity of 750km/s and maximum IMF strength of 13nT as documented from the ICME catalogue. Additionally, an SIR/CIR events of 41 is being noted.

Table – 3.5: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2013.

2013	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$54.05^{+3.5}_{-4.0}$	54	0.397	$103.09^{+10.5}_{-13.1}$	102.989	0.152	$51.28^{+3.6}_{-4.2}$	51.230	0.285
B_y	$123.45^{+8.5}_{-9.8}$	123.333	0.235	$243.90^{+31.1}_{-41.8}$	243.658	0.347	$95.23^{+6.7}_{-7.8}$	95.142	0.210
B_z	$98.03^{+6.2}_{-7.2}$	97.941	0.255	$163.93^{+21.0}_{-28.3}$	163.770	0.190	$71.42^{+4.3}_{-4.9}$	71.357	0.286
Proton Density	$114.94^{+11.8}_{-14.9}$	114.827	0.171	$119.04^{+14.8}_{-19.8}$	118.928	0.351	$80^{+6.4}_{-7.7}$	79.920	0.223
Proton Speed	$243.9^{+21.6}_{-26.3}$	243.658	0.086	$263.15^{+40.9}_{-59.4}$	262.894	0.650	$163.93^{+16.8}_{-21.2}$	163.770	0.199
Alpha Proton Density	$65.35^{+5.8}_{-7.1}$	65.294	0.171	$76.92^{+10.2}_{-13.9}$	76.846	0.621	$65.35^{+5.1}_{-6.0}$	65.294	0.169

In 2013 as detailed in Table 3.5, the satellite separation between the two satellites ACE and wind is found to be $50R_E$ to $240 R_E$, the correlation lengths for the IMF components follow the order $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{SIR} > \lambda_{Amb}$, regarding proton density, the sequence is reversed: $\lambda_{ICME} (N_p) > \lambda_{SIR} (N_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (N_p)$, Similarly, for proton speed, $\lambda_{ICME} (V_p) > \lambda_{SIR} (V_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (V_p)$, Additionally, concerning the alpha proton density ratio, $\lambda_{ICME} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{SIR}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb} (n_{He}/n_H)$. The correlation length values of ICMEs, SIRs, and the ambient solar wind mostly have a similar trend without substantial deviation. However, it can be noted that ICME has a very high correlation length as a consequence of it being a large-scale event with coherent structures. SIRs exhibit moderate turbulence from their interaction with the solar wind and compression of the wave [Maggiolo et al., 2017]. In the meantime, ambient solar wind shows the least value as it is homogeneous without any special structures and is affected by small-scale turbulence and interaction [Maggiolo et al., 2017], representing a background state of solar wind.

The R^2 values for all events are below 0.65, indicating a reliable fit, although a few events have R^2 values under 0.3. The plot depicting the correlation length versus satellite separation is shown below from Fig: 3.7 to Fig: 3.12.

Fig 3.7: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_x for the year 2013 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.8: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_y for the year 2013 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.9: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_z for the year 2013 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.10: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for proton density for the year 2013 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.11: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for proton speed for the year 2013 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.12: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for alpha proton density ratio for the year 2013 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

The year 2014 marks the solar maximum year of the solar cycle with an annual average sunspot number of 113.3 and alongside 21 ICME events and 36 SIR/CIR events. The maximum velocity of the solar wind for ICME is 720km/s and maximum IMF strength of 20nT. The correlation length with positive and negative error, decorrelation length with R^2 value is analysed in the table 3.6.

Table – 3.6: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2014

2014	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$99.00^{+8.1}_{-9.6}$	98.910	0.254	$135.13^{+17.4}_{-23.5}$	135	0.377	$45.24^{+2.8}_{-3.2}$	45.203	0.180
B_y	$125.00^{+10.0}_{-11.9}$	124.875	0.023	$227.27^{+38.5}_{-58.4}$	227.045	0.462	$62.50^{+4.0}_{-4.6}$	62.437	0.444
B_z	$121.95^{+10.8}_{-13.1}$	121.829	0.482	$204.08^{+34.5}_{-52.3}$	203.877	0.025	$59.52^{+3.3}_{-3.7}$	59.464	0.289
Proton Density	$119.04^{+12.6}_{-16.0}$	118.928	0.388	$151.51^{+23.3}_{-33.6}$	151.363	0.046	$66.22^{+5.2}_{-6.2}$	66.158	0.274
Proton Speed	$238.09^{+25.3}_{-32.1}$	237.857	0.322	$200.33^{+32.8}_{-48.0}$	208.125	0.045	$99.00^{+8.9}_{-10.8}$	98.910	0.146
Alpha Proton Density	$55.24^{+5.9}_{-7.6}$	55.193	0.454	$151.51^{+23.3}_{-33.6}$	151.363	0.046	$49.01^{+3.9}_{-4.7}$	48.970	0.115

In 2014, detailed in Table 3.6, the separation range between the satellites is $30 R_E$ to $142 R_E$, and the correlation lengths for the IMF components exhibit the sequence $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{SIR} > \lambda_{Amb}$, Concerning proton density, $\lambda_{ICME} (N_p) > \lambda_{SIR} (N_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (N_p)$. However, for proton speed, $\lambda_{SIR} (V_p) > \lambda_{ICME} (V_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (V_p)$. Additionally, regarding the alpha proton density ratio, $\lambda_{ICME} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{SIR} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb} (n_{He}/n_H)$. During 2014, a solar maximum year, the correlation lengths for all parameters except proton speed follow a general trend where the correlation length is highest for ICMEs, followed by SIRs, and the ambient solar wind. For proton speed, however, the correlation length is highest for SIRs, followed by ICMEs, and the ambient solar wind. This could be so because various solar wind structures might have different origins and dynamics. Fast solar wind streams interacting with slower solar wind streams generate SIRs. Fast solar wind could overtake slower streams during interaction [Maggiolo et al., 2017], increasing proton speeds by accelerating the protons [Richardson, 2018]. This significant increase in proton speed may be due to the compression and dynamic interaction within super-intense regions. This enhances proton speed even more leading to much higher correlation length proton speed in SIR events than in ICMEs. Contrary to this, ICMEs, which are large solar eruptions, might decelerate through the interplanetary medium upon encountering surrounding solar wind [Maggiolo et al., 2017]. The deceleration might be associated with the drag and interaction of the surrounding solar wind material, resulting in the proton speed within the ICME to decrease to a level lower than that observed inside SIRs [Gopalswamy et al., 2000; Perri et al., 2023].

In contrast to SIR and ICME, ambient solar wind is background solar wind, a steadier and persistent stream of solar wind without transient perturbations. As a result, a less dynamic, slower, and less demanding regime in the ambient solar wind results in the proton speeds being generally low [Richardson, 2018]. The R^2 values are below 0.5, which means a fairly good fit.

The next analysis for the year 2015 is done which falls on the peak year of the solar cycle 24 with an annual average sunspot number is 69.8 accompanied by 30 ICME events and 48 SIR/CIR events retrieved from the catalogue mentioned earlier. The ICME has a maximum solar wind velocity of 740 km/s and a maximum IMF strength of 20 nT noted from the catalogue. The correlation length, decorrelation length and R^2 value are analysed and tabulated in Table 3.7.

Table – 3.7: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2015

2015	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$49.75^{+2.3}_{-2.6}$	49.701	0.388	$60.97^{+6.3}_{-7.9}$	60.914	0.377	$46.08^{+2.6}_{-2.9}$	46.036	0.041
B_y	$109.89^{+6.7}_{-7.7}$	109.780	0.118	$156.25^{+21.1}_{-28.9}$	156.093	0.246	$76.92^{+4.4}_{-5.0}$	76.846	0.224
B_z	$87.71^{+5.0}_{-5.7}$	87.631	0.177	$100.0^{+10.7}_{-13.6}$	99.900	0.414	$64.93^{+3.5}_{-4.0}$	64.870	0.307
Proton Density	$120.48^{+10.5}_{-12.8}$	120.361	0.181	$131.57^{+15.2}_{-19.9}$	131.447	0.416	$102.04^{+7.7}_{-9.0}$	101.938	0.212
Proton Speed	$227.27^{+18.9}_{-22.7}$	227.045	0.197	$250.0^{+37.2}_{-53.0}$	249.750	0.166	$140.84^{+10.9}_{-13.0}$	140.704	0.150
Alpha Proton Density	$61.34^{+3.8}_{-4.4}$	61.288	0.216	$66.6^{+8.1}_{-10.8}$	66.600	0.566	$61.72^{+3.9}_{-4.4}$	61.666	0.347

In 2015 as tabulated in Table 3.7, the separation between the satellites varied from 50 R_E to 230 R_E , the correlation lengths for the IMF B_x show: $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{SIR} > \lambda_{Amb}$, for IMF components along B_y and B_z , the order is $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{SIR} > \lambda_{Amb}$. Regarding, proton density, $\lambda_{ICME} (N_p) > \lambda_{SIR} (N_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (N_p)$, additionally for proton speed $\lambda_{ICME} (V_p) > \lambda_{SIR} (V_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (V_p)$. Furthermore, in terms of the alpha proton density ratio, $\lambda_{ICME} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{SIR} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb} (n_{He}/n_H)$. All the parameters observed show a general trend where the correlation length for ICME is higher than SIR which is higher than ambient solar wind. The R^2 value is below 0.6 showing good fit with few below 0.3.

For 2016, the average annual sunspot number was 39.8, which dropped significantly after the peak solar years. The total number of ICME events is 13 with a maximum solar wind speed of 570 km/s and a maximum IMF strength of 20 nT derived from the aforementioned catalogue. There are 49 SIR/CIR events, where the SIR number dominates the ICME events. The investigation of the correlation length with positive and negative error and decorrelation length with R^2 value are analysed and tabulated in 3.8.

Table – 3.8: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2016

2016	SIR			ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$54.64^{+2.8}_{-3.1}$	54.590	0.267	$97.08^{+14.4}_{-20.5}$	96.990	0.109	$33.67^{+1.9}_{-2.1}$	33.636	0.111
B_y	$101.01^{+6.6}_{-7.8}$	100.909	0.281	$222.22^{+33.5}_{-48.0}$	222	0.229	$73.52^{+4.5}_{-5.2}$	73.455	0.206
B_z	$78.12^{+4.5}_{-5.2}$	78.046	0.118	$153.84^{+27.2}_{-42.2}$	153.692	0.219	$55.86^{+3.2}_{-3.6}$	55.810	0.241
Proton Density	$128.20^{+10.5}_{-12.6}$	128.076	0.103	$163.93^{+34.0}_{-58.2}$	163.770	0.213	$114.94^{+8.5}_{-10.0}$	114.827	0.086
Proton Speed	$232.55^{+19.7}_{-23.8}$	232.325	0.123	$277.77^{+60.3}_{-92.5}$	277.500	0.216	$161.29^{+14.2}_{-17.2}$	161.129	0.261
Alpha Proton Density	$70.42^{+4.6}_{-5.3}$	70.352	0.290	$54.34^{+8.4}_{-12.3}$	54.293	0.299	$73.52^{+4.5}_{-5.2}$	73.455	0.302

In 2016 the detailed tabulation is done in Table 3.8, the separation between the satellite was observed to be $50 R_E$ to $140 R_E$, the correlation length for the IMF component demonstrates $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{SIR} > \lambda_{Amb}$, regarding proton density, $\lambda_{ICME} (N_p) > \lambda_{SIR} (N_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (N_p)$, while for proton speed, $\lambda_{ICME} (V_p) > \lambda_{SIR} (V_p) > \lambda_{Amb} (V_p)$, Contrary to, the alpha proton density ratio follows the order $\lambda_{Amb} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{SIR} (n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{ICME} (n_{He}/n_H)$. This might be because the ambient solar wind is steadier and uniform, and such stability allows for correlation to be sustained over large distances as it is less affected by turbulence or significant structural disruptions [J. J. Podesta et al., 2008]. The R^2 value is less than 0.3 forecasting an unreliable fit. The plot representing the correlation length versus the satellite separation is shown in Fig: 3.13 to Fig: 3.18.

Fig 3.13: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_x for the year 2016 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.14: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_y for the year 2016 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.15: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for IMF B_x for the year 2016 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.16: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for proton density for the year 2016 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.17: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for proton speed for the year 2016 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

Fig 3.18: Correlation coefficient versus separation between the two satellites (R_E) for alpha proton density ratio for the year 2016 for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind (from left to right)

The year 2017 has an annual sunspot number of 21.7 and is characterised by a return to weak solar conditions marking the beginning of the solar minimum with total ICME events being 9, a maximum solar wind velocity of 800 km/s and an IMF strength of 16 nT. The SIR/CIR events data are not available for this year and after. Initial observations are discussed, and Table 3.9 shows the correlation length with errors, decorrelation length, and R^2 value.

Table – 3.9: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2017

2017	ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$131.57^{+24.0}_{-37.9}$	131.447	0.167	$53.76^{+9.1}_{-13.8}$	53.709	0.364
B_y	$204.08^{+50.2}_{-98.9}$	203.877	0.539	$46.29^{+5.1}_{-6.6}$	46.250	0.039
B_z	$97.08^{+20.7}_{-36.2}$	96.990	0.160	$51.81^{+4.8}_{-5.9}$	51.761	0.163
Proton Density	$153.84^{+38.9}_{-78.7}$	153.692	0.352	$97.08^{+20.7}_{-36.2}$	96.990	0.120
Proton Speed	$416.66^{+138.8}_{-208.3}$	416.250	0.603	$106.38^{+19.4}_{-30.6}$	106.276	0.194
Alpha Proton Density	$116.27^{+26.1}_{-27.6}$	116.162	0.247	$42.01^{+4.7}_{-6.0}$	41.974	0.079

Year 2017 is detailed in Table 3.9, the separation between the satellite is $40 R_E$ to $141 R_E$, the correlation length for the IMF component indicates that for IMF B_x : $\lambda_{ICME}(B_x) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_x)$, while for IMF components along B_y and B_z , $\lambda_{ICME} > \lambda_{Amb}$, concerning proton density, $\lambda_{ICME}(N_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(N_p)$, and proton speed, $\lambda_{ICME}(V_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(V_p)$, Moreover, the alpha proton density ratio follows the pattern where $\lambda_{ICME}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{Amb}(n_{He}/n_H)$. The list of SIRs data is not present from 2017 to 2019.

From the table, it can be observed that the correlation length of ICME is higher than ambient solar wind in all the cases showing a familiar trend. For proton speed, the correlation length exceeds $300R_E$ i.e., $416 R_E$, with an error of $+138.8 R_E$ and $-208.3 R_E$, this may be due to the unavailability of enough data points for that event parameter due to a quiet solar minimum year. The R^2 value is mostly found to be less than 0.3, except for ICME proton speed when the R^2 value is 0.6.

The annual sunspot number for 2018 is 7, making it the solar minimum year for solar cycle 24, similar to that of 2009. Solar activity is very low, with 8 ICME events, a maximum solar wind velocity of 460km/s , and an IMF strength of 16nT . Table 3.10 analyses and compares the correlation length with errors, decorrelation length, and R^2 value.

Table – 3.10: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2018

2018	ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$188.67^{+29.9}_{-43.8}$	188.490	0.277	$79.36^{+14.4}_{-22.6}$	79.285	0.256
B_y	$263.15^{+45.7}_{-70.1}$	262.894	0.316	$66.22^{+13.8}_{-23.8}$	66.158	0.315
B_z	$158.73^{+28.8}_{-45.3}$	158.571	0.166	$93.45^{+17.1}_{-27.0}$	93.364	0.138
Proton Density	$166.66^{+61.4}_{-18.8}$	166.500	0.145	$66.22^{+15.7}_{-29.9}$	66.158	0.069
Proton Speed	$434.78^{+122.2}_{-231.8}$	434.347	0.214	$196.07^{+46.8}_{-89.6}$	195.882	0.150
Alpha Proton Density	$64.10^{+10.9}_{-16.5}$	64.038	0.058	$80.00^{+15.8}_{-26.3}$	79.920	0.399

In 2018, the average separation between the two satellites was $45 R_E$ to $140 R_E$, and the detailed correlation length is tabulated in Table 3.10. The correlation length for the IMF component reveals that for the IMF B_x , $\lambda_{ICME}(B_x) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_x)$, for the IMF B_y is $\lambda_{ICME}(B_y) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_y)$ and the IMF B_z is $\lambda_{ICME}(B_z) > \lambda_{Amb}(B_z)$. Regarding proton density, $\lambda_{ICME}(N_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(N_p)$, for proton speed $\lambda_{ICME}(V_p) > \lambda_{Amb}(V_p)$. Additionally, the alpha proton density ratio demonstrates that $\lambda_{Amb}(n_{He}/n_H) > \lambda_{ICME}(n_{He}/n_H)$. A discrepancy is noticed for proton velocity, because of the unavailability of ICME events since it is a quiet year, which exceeds correlation length values cited in previous work. Here, the correlation length for proton velocity for the ICME event is found to be $434.78 R_E$ with an error of approximately $+122.2R_E$ and $-231.8 R_E$. The remaining parameters reveal a common trend of ICME correlation length higher than ambient solar wind. R^2 is lower than 0.4, indicating a good fit.

Solar cycle 24 will end in 2019 with an annual average sunspot number of 3.6, an ICME occurrence of 7, a peak solar wind speed of 560 km/s , and an IMF of 12 nT . Table 3.11, which summarises the analysis of the solar events, contrasts the ICME and ambient solar wind correlation length with positive and negative error, decorrelation length, and R^2 .

Table – 3.11: Decorrelation length table for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind for 2019

2019	ICME			Ambient Solar Wind		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$112.35^{+23.8}_{-41.4}$	112.247	0.360	$50.00^{+7.4}_{-10.6}$	49.950	0.265
B_y	$74.62^{+17.48}_{-32.6}$	74.552	0.200	$49.01^{+8.3}_{-12.7}$	48.970	0.352
B_z	$101.04^{+20.7}_{-34.9}$	101.938	0.188	$64.93^{+7.4}_{-9.6}$	64.870	0.214
Proton Density	$86.20^{+24.4}_{-56.2}$	86.120	0.303	$54.94^{+10.3}_{-16.4}$	54.890	0.655
Proton Speed	$294.11^{+81.35}_{-42.22}$	293.823	0.144	$151.51^{+41.6}_{-92.3}$	151.363	0.023
Alpha Proton Density	$72.46^{+17.5}_{-33.9}$	72.391	0.084	$33.78^{+3.9}_{-5.1}$	33.750	0.155

In 2019, the average separation between the satellites is from 35R_E to 135 R_E, and the correlation length of the events is tabulated in Table 3.11. The IMF B_x, B_y, and B_z correlation lengths indicate that $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} > \lambda_{\text{Amb}}$. Regarding proton density, $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (N_p) > \lambda_{\text{Amb}} (N_p)$, whereas for proton speed, $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (V_p) > \lambda_{\text{Amb}} (V_p)$. Additionally, the alpha proton density ratio illustrates that $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}}) > \lambda_{\text{Amb}} (n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}})$. It shows a similar trend where the correlation length for ICME is higher than ambient solar wind. The R² values are less than 0.35 indicating an unreliable fit because of the scattering of data points and high variation in solar wind.

Across the years 2009 to 2019, a common trend in the correlation lengths (λ_c) for the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) components indicates that λ_{ICME} tends to be greater than λ_{SIR} , which, in turn, tends to be greater than λ_{Amb} . This pattern is consistent for most components and years, suggesting a general ordering trend.

But for particular cases, some exceptions have been recorded to this pattern, for instance in 2010 wherein for the IMF B_z, $\lambda_{\text{SIR}} (B_z)$ is longer than $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (B_z)$, which is longer than $\lambda_{\text{amb}} (B_z)$. Moreover, for 2018, the deviation has been observed in the alpha proton density ratio pattern, where $\lambda_{\text{Amb}} (n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}})$ surpasses $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}})$. These deviations imply that the correlation length along the IMF components may not always follow the same order, suggesting complex and dynamic interactions within the solar wind. Other deviations have been explained above.

Concerning proton density, there is a consistent reversal in the order between $\lambda_{\text{SIR}} (N_p)$ and $\lambda_{\text{Amb}} (N_p)$ compared to $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (N_p)$, observed across most years. Additionally, for proton speed, $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (V_p)$ often exceeds $\lambda_{\text{SIR}} (V_p)$ which, in turn, exceeds $\lambda_{\text{Amb}} (V_p)$.

Moreover, the alpha proton density ratio follows a similar trend across most years, with $\lambda_{\text{ICME}} (n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}})$ typically longer than $\lambda_{\text{SIR}} (n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}})$, which is longer than $\lambda_{\text{Amb}} (n_{\text{He}}/n_{\text{H}})$. This indicates a degree of consistency in the composition of solar wind plasma under different interplanetary conditions.

3.2 DISCUSSION

The correlation length in the solar wind is crucial since it allows us to determine the spatial scales over which the magnetic field remains coherent, which indicates the size of coherent magnetic field structures [Wicks et al., 2009]. It is a critical parameter for heliospheric models, establishing a scale that must be precisely captured. Moreover, it represents the typical size of energy-containing structures interacting with planetary magnetospheres [Wicks et al., 2010].

Investing in solar wind correlation length over the solar cycle helps to understand how solar wind influences the Earth's magnetosphere. It reveals how magnetic field coherence evolves over time and influences the directional response of the Earth's magnetic field. Finding the correlation length changes throughout the solar cycle helps identify its underlying causes and understand the dynamics of the effects in the magnetosphere [Wicks et al., 2010].

The correlation length of the magnetic field within the solar wind stimulates the behaviour of the path of solar energetic particles. A precise estimation of correlation length is essential for understanding the spatial and temporal variation to predict the solar wind dynamics and offer valuable insight. Correlation length modelling helps to understand the nature of interplanetary turbulence and explore the implications for the transport and acceleration of energetic particles. The insights derived from correlation length led to a profound understanding of the heliosphere structure and dynamics, facilitating the heliospheric magnetic field and the interstellar medium interaction. This knowledge helps forecast space weather events and gives an overview of their potential impact on Earth's magnetosphere and ionosphere.

Extensive research has been done previously, focusing on the empirical determination of the correlation coefficient and correlation length by Matthaeus, 1986, to enhance the understanding of the solar winds' magnetic field characteristics and their implications for space weather monitoring and prediction.

Previous research has typically reported correlation lengths for various solar wind parameters in the range of 100 to 300 R_E , Matthaeus et al., 2005 identified typical correlation lengths for magnetic field fluctuations around 200 R_E . The correlation

lengths of approximately 265 R_E have been reported for Elsässer variables, incorporated in magnetic field and velocity fluctuations.

For specific solar wind conditions, the correlation length has been around 265 R_E as reported by Tu and Marsch, 1995. Goldstein et al., 1995, reported another correlation length for different solar wind parameters, such as magnetic field and velocity fluctuation, ranging from 100 R_E to 200 R_E . Milano et al., 2004, found that the correlation length for magnetic field fluctuation is approximately 200 R_E , an observation that Matthaeus et al., 2005 confirmed.

The derivation of correlation length depends on the different measurement techniques employed and the variability of the solar wind. The correlation length of plasma parameters and magnetic fields varies from 100 R_E to 300 R_E , according to Weygand et al., 2009. Also, in the recent study by Wicks et al., 2009, the correlation length was observed to be up to 274 R_E with a positive error of 104 R_E and a negative error of -59 R_E with an uncertainty of 0.49. The above studies on correlation length have collectively provided a comprehensive understanding of the solar wind parameters and have emphasized the variability and the factors that influence the solar wind measurement.

Again, *Amara Graps*, 1995, has detailed the dimensions of the halo orbits, which are about 31.39 R_E (200,000 km) along the ecliptic in the Earth-Sun direction (x-direction), 108.33 R_E (650,000 km) along the ecliptic perpendicular to the Earth-Sun direction (y - direction), and stretch 32.40 R_E (200,000 km) out of the ecliptic (z-direction). Understanding the correlation length of solar wind parameters is important for space weather predictions and studies of how the underlying process interacts with the Earth's magnetosphere.

Here, the data is analyzed from 2009 to 2019 for solar cycle 24, and the average

Fig 3.19: ACE (orange) and WIND (blue) satellite location in the L1 orbit in X_{GSE} and Y_{GSE} coordinates along the ecliptic to the Earth-Sun direction (x - direction).

Courtesy: https://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/Locator_graphics.cgi

separation between the two satellites, ACE and WIND, ranges from 30 R_E to 240 R_E . It has been observed, from the findings that, as the average separation between the satellites increases, the correlation values for all the parameters decrease across all the solar events, highlighting an inverse relationship between the average satellite separation and correlation for parameters across solar cycle 24. The satellites' orientations for ACE (in orange) and Wind (in blue) are illustrated in figures 3.19 to 3.21, where the Sun is at the origin (0,0) and the Earth at (1AU, 0) obtained from the space physics data facility of NASA at 'https://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/Locator_graphics.cgi'.

Satellites in the L1 region provide critical upstream solar wind data. The figures from 3.19 to 3.21 display the orbital trajectories of the ACE and the Wind satellites in the L1 region in GSE coordinates in R_E . This visualisation is essential in understanding the relative positioning and distribution of the two spacecraft, playing a crucial role in assessing the correlation length of the observed solar wind data. As the correlation of solar wind parameters such as density, velocity, etc., depends on the separation between the satellites, the trajectories in figures 3.19 to 3.21 underscore the significance of their positioning for simultaneous multi-satellite observation. The satellite trajectory figures implicitly demonstrate how the satellite's orbit evolves over time, affecting the separation and the correlation between their measurements.

Fig 3.20: ACE (orange) and WIND (blue) satellite location in the L1 orbit in X_{GSE} and Z_{GSE} coordinates out of the ecliptic to the Earth-Sun direction (z-direction). Courtesy: https://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/Locator_graphics.cgi

A clear outline for the solar wind structure has been observed by incorporating spatiotemporal analysis into these events over the entire solar cycle. Distinct trends were observed for ICMEs, SIRs, and ambient solar wind events that indicate the turbulent and dynamic nature of the solar wind. The ICME has the longest correlation length among the three categories of events, indicating a large spatial influence. SIRs have moderate correlation length and, thus moderate spatial influence relative to ICMEs. In ambient solar wind, the correlation length is significantly short, indicating a strongly localized influence of the ambient solar wind conditions. The yearly interpretation of such events gives the following definitive insight.

Fig 3.21: ACE (orange) and WIND (blue) satellite location in the L1 orbit in Y_{GSE} and Z_{GSE} coordinates perpendicular to the ecliptic to the Earth-Sun direction (y-direction). Courtesy: https://sscweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/Locator_graphics.cgi

ICME displays a longer correlation length compared to SIR and ambient solar wind, indicating ICME is characterised by greater coherence and ordered structures that would lead to intense and more predictable interaction with Earth's magnetosphere [Rout, 2017; Borovsky, 2020].

Contrary to this, SIR demonstrates significant variability, thus a more unstable and less homogeneous structure. The variability of a correlation length with large fluctuation over time represents a dynamic interaction and turbulence within this region.

The ambient solar wind exhibits relatively steady parameters with shorter correlation lengths, typically shorter than those of ICME and SIR. It exhibits less variation than SIR, suggesting more stable magnetic field structures characteristic of a more uniform background state. The stability of the ambient solar wind offers a baseline against which more dynamic solar wind structures can be compared.

The correlation length of the ICME and SIR/CIR has been observed to be higher than the nominal halo orbit dimension mentioned by Amara Graps, 1995, and also higher than the average satellite separation. This might be because ICMEs often include magnetic clouds, characterised by helical or twisted magnetic field lines [Borovsky, 2020]; regions that are large-scale with structured and organised magnetic fields and plasma structures spanning considerable distances [Pedersen, et al., 2020]. The large-scale structures have relatively coherent magnetic fields which can reach beyond the typical spatial scale observed during quiet solar conditions, leading to heightened correlation lengths. The enormous size of the ICME could result in dwarfing the dimensions of typical halo orbits. ICME has flux rope structures that are twisted magnetic structures with internal magnetic tension that keeps them coherent over large distances and stays connected over large areas, which is responsible for the large correlation length observed [Qiang Hu et al., 2015]. The correlation length is often measured by the extent to which similar features are observed by both spacecraft. Solar wind features can change over time but also retain spatial coherence over longer distances larger than a halo orbit, with the result that two satellites positioned at different points along the orbit of Earth will be able to detect the same ICME travelling through space as it is enormous, reflecting the longer correlation length [J. J. Podesta, et al., 2008; Paul Geyer et al., 2021]. Measured correlation lengths agree with past reported values above. Intensive analysis and monitoring of SIR variability must be performed to better precisely forecast space weather.

A high correlation length indicates solar wind velocity is coherent over a large distance. The large coherence of the solar wind velocity strongly relates to the solar wind structure being stable over long spatial distances. This suggests the extended occurrence of large-scale, coherent solar wind streams can strongly influence space weather, leading to extended geomagnetic storms if they encounter Earth's magnetosphere.

A striking trend is observed in the ICME data for proton density and alpha-proton density ratio correlation lengths. A steep decrease is observed for values of correlation lengths of proton density and a tremendous rise in correlation length for the alpha-proton density ratio when compared in ICME and SIR. This has been noticed in 2010 data, in which the correlation length of events under the ICME category is lower than that of SIR. In 2018 too, the alpha-proton density ratio correlation length of event

ICME was smaller than ambient solar wind events, adhering to the same trend and providing signature evidence of magnetic cloud presence [Rout, 2017].

Observations obtained from ACE and WIND satellites indicate extensive scatter in the observation, which is challenging for making reliable estimations of correlation length. There has been a large uncertainty in the R^2 value, some on a large scale, mainly as a result of scatter in measurement, due to the highly variable solar wind. This turbulent character of the solar wind results from constant density and magnetic field component fluctuations. The fluctuation of R^2 is influenced by the intricate interplay between locally developing turbulence and large-scale features originating in the Sun. Therefore, there exists considerable variation in the correlation length observed within the solar wind. This scattering of the correlation coefficient for the observed events can highlight the dynamic and complex nature of the solar wind environment assigned to the temporal evolution and spatial distribution of the solar wind properties.

The study captures the variation of correlation lengths across Solar Cycle 24, offering a comprehensive view of the solar cycle's influence on solar wind dynamics. Owing to the decorrelation lengths, the study significantly contributes to its ability to comprehend better the mechanisms of energy cascades in the solar wind, including the shift from coherent regimes, dominated by large-scale structures such as ICMEs and CIRs, to stochastic regimes. Most events in this chapter exhibit universal patterns of event-specific behaviours, with only a few identified exceptions and their causes being explained.

The study can be used to demonstrate the variation of the correlation length for the entire solar cycle 24, as it exhibits clear properties of the solar cycle in terms of well-defined differences between the solar maximum and solar minimum periods. Further intricacies and fluctuations in the measurement of correlation length for solar wind are derived from observing the solar cycle variation at different phases explained in Chapter -4.

3.3 CONCLUSION

This chapter analyses the correlation/decorrelation lengths of the solar wind turbulence during solar cycle 24, focusing on the ICME, SIR/CIR and the ambient solar wind events utilizing the multi-spacecraft data from ACE and WIND satellites. The analysis reveals key findings on the local spatial features and turbulence characteristics within the heliosphere, by applying the advance spatiotemporal methods and the windowing technique mentioned in detailed in Chapter-2.

A weak solar cycle with reduced solar activity and turbulence can significantly alter the magnetohydrodynamic cascade process within the heliosphere. The distribution of the energy among the different scales of the plasma can be affected by the weak solar wind conditions modifying the turbulence features. A reduced correlation length, which signifies heightened turbulence dissipation, implies that long-range interactions within the plasma are less persistent. This can lead to a disruption in the transfer of energy from large-scale to small-scale structures.

However, an extended correlation length, indicating greater coherence in plasma structures, suggests that energy can be more efficiently transferred across larger distances. The interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) intensity is reduced during periods of weak solar activity, influencing the dynamics and evolution of turbulence.

Therefore, exceptions have been observed in the trends for different parameters showing inhomogeneity in the IMF parameters, especially for proton density and alpha-proton density ratio, when analysed for each year for the solar cycle 24. The analysis on the chapter identifies cases where the expected ordering of correlation lengths among the ICME, SIR/CIR and ambient solar wind have been reversed contrary to the common trend. These deviations may imply that the correlation lengths along the IMF components may not always follow the same order, suggesting complex and dynamic interactions within the solar wind. The turbulent nature of the solar wind causes persistent fluctuations in density and magnetic field components. This has been pointed out and clarified within the chapter.

The study also noted the impact of weak solar wind conditions during solar cycle 24 on turbulence features, influencing magnetohydrodynamic cascade processes [Bruno

& Carbone, 2013]. Furthermore, the R^2 values, consistently below 0.5, indicated measurement scatter due to the highly variable nature of the solar wind. The turbulent nature of the solar wind is caused by persistent fluctuations in density and magnetic field components. The variation of R^2 may be affected by the complex interaction between locally evolving turbulence and large-scale structures coming from the Sun. This knowledge helps forecast space weather events and gives an overview of their potential impact on Earth's magnetosphere and ionosphere.

Ultimately, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of heliospheric structure and dynamics, facilitating improved space weather forecasting and insights into the potential impact of solar events on Earth's magnetosphere and ionosphere. The observed variations in correlation lengths across the solar cycle underscore the dynamic nature of solar wind turbulence and its implications for space weather phenomena.

Following on from Chapter 3's year-by-year correlation length estimation of different solar wind structures is to examine how these correlation qualities vary over larger time scales, particularly the phases of a solar cycle. The changes in solar wind parameter spatial coherence during the maximum and minimum phase, and ascending, and descending phases of Solar Cycle 24 are investigated in Chapter 4. A more thorough understanding of how long-term solar activity evolves solar wind structure and, consequently, the correlation length of solar wind is made possible by this temporal segmentation. Connecting event-based space weather signatures to the dynamics of the global solar cycle requires these understanding. Chapter 4 investigation of the variation of the correlation length/decorrelation length on the different phases of the Solar Cycle 24.

Chapter 4:

Variation in decorrelation lengths in solar maximum and minimum:

Many complex interactions between the Sun's magnetic field and its plasma happen in the 11-year solar cycle. Evidence suggests the interaction between fast and slow solar wind, hence altering the complexity of the solar wind throughout various solar cycle phases [Wicks et al., 2009]. The solar cycle begins solar minimum in the initial years of the solar cycle with minimum solar activity. The ascending phase starts after the solar minimum, as solar activity rises, leading to the solar maximum at its peak year of the cycle, with frequent solar flares and CME eruptions. Following the solar maximum, the sunspot number begins to decrease leading to the solar minimum. The solar wind is a turbulent plasma influenced by the solar cycle. The charged particles the Sun emits are influenced by the solar cycle, which also influences the entire heliosphere.

Scrutinising the different phases of the solar cycle helps to understand the generation and evolution of solar magnetic fields. Solar activity and turbulence are closely related as a result of the solar dynamo process, the creation of magnetic fields, and the dynamics of plasma. The interaction of the magnetic field produced by the solar dynamo process with the plasma motion causes increased turbulence at solar maximum, hence converting large-scale motions into smaller-scale energies. Crucially in wave-particle interactions, solar wind plasma defines the distribution and dissipation of energy in space plasmas. Therefore, a thorough study of several phases of the solar cycle is conducted to understand how turbulence in the solar wind develops, affecting particle acceleration and energy transfer mechanisms [Zhao, 2018]. Evaluating solar wind parameters and the interaction between developing turbulence and coronal drivers depends on understanding the spatial correlation of the flow fluctuations [Wicks et al., 2009].

To investigate the various phases of the solar cycle, we divided them into two sets, each comprising two categories: the solar maximum and minimum phases, followed by the ascending and descending phases.

For the first category, the solar maximums of 2013, 2014, and 2015 are being considered because they occur during the peak years of solar cycle 24. And for solar minimum 2010, 2011, and 2016 are being considered. 2010 and 2011 fall during the solar minimum period and have sufficient data for evaluation. 2016 is considered because no data for SIR is available in the catalogue [Chi et al., 2018] after 2016.

In the second category, the ascending phase, where solar activity gradually starts increasing, the years 2011 and 2012 are considered, and the descending phase, where solar activity gradually starts decreasing, the years 2015 and 2016 are considered for investigation.

4.1 RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS:

A comparative study is made in Table 4.1 for SIR events during solar maximum and solar minimum. From the table, it can be observed that the parameters for the SIR event IMF B_y , IMF B_z , and proton speed, follow a general trend where the correlation length for solar maximum λ_{\max} is greater than the correlation length of solar minimum λ_{\min} , i.e., $\lambda_{\max} > \lambda_{\min}$. Contrary to it, IMF B_x , proton density, and alpha-proton density ratio, the correlation lengths during the solar minimum (λ_{\min}) are greater than those during the solar maximum (λ_{\max}), i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$. The exception observed where the reverse is true, i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$, indicates a peculiar behaviour. The complicated wind structures of SIR could be the cause of the IMF B_x displaying this disparity. Fast and slow solar wind stream interaction enhances the turbulence in SIR formation [Kavanagh et al., 2007; Sanchez-Diaz et al., 2016] during solar maximum. This disrupts IMF B_x 's coherence, resulting in reduced correlation length during the solar maximum year [Sanchez-Diaz et al., 2016].

Alpha particles and protons can maintain more stable and coherent interaction throughout long distances during the solar minimum because of more transient days, less interactions, and less mixing [Kavanagh et al., 2007], hence generating a longer correlation length. Coronal holes are recurrent close to solar minimums [Kavanagh et al., 2007], therefore these discrepancies suggest that CIRs have a dominant role during solar minimum years.

Table 4.1: Decorrelation length for solar minimum and solar maximum for SIR.

SIR	Solar Minimum			Solar Maximum		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$73.52^{+3.1}_{-3.3}$	73.455	0.467	$60.97^{+2.4}_{-2.7}$	60.914	0.596
B_y	$84.74^{+4.1}_{-4.5}$	84.661	0.407	$117.64^{+5.2}_{-5.8}$	117.529	0.495
B_z	$84.74^{+3.4}_{-3.7}$	84.661	0.477	$98.03^{+3.6}_{-4.0}$	97.941	0.374
Proton Density	$123.45^{+8.5}_{-9.8}$	123.333	0.398	$119.04^{+6.6}_{-7.5}$	118.928	0.537
Proton Speed	$243.90^{+16.6}_{-19.2}$	243.658	0.527	$250^{+17.4}_{-20.2}$	249.750	0.522
Alpha Proton Density	$72.46^{+4.4}_{-5.0}$	72.391	0.287	$60.97^{+3.1}_{-3.5}$	60.914	0.513

A comparison between each parameter is shown in Figure 4.1, with the green line representing the solar minimum and the red line representing the solar maximum. For most cases, the solar maximum correlation length is more than the solar minimum in the SIR/CIR event.

Fig 4.1: Variation of SIR/CIR parameters for B_x , B_y , B_z , proton density, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio for solar maximum (red) and solar minimum (green).

Table 4.2: Decorrelation length for solar minimum and solar maximum for ICME events.

ICME	Solar Minimum			Solar Maximum		
	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	119.04 ^{+10.3} _{-12.5}	118.928	0.171	90.90 ^{+6.1} _{-7.1}	90.818	0.481
B_y	144.92 ^{+13.3} _{-16.3}	144.782	0.404	204.08 ^{+18.8} _{-23.1}	203.877	0.448
B_z	126.58 ^{+12.9} _{-16.2}	126.455	0.448	142.85 ^{+11.2} _{-13.3}	142.714	0.031
Proton Density	106.38 ^{+13.7} _{-18.6}	106.276	0.101	131.57 ^{+9.6} _{-11.2}	131.447	0.501
Proton Speed	250.90 ^{+27.7} _{-35.7}	249.750	0.275	243.90 ^{+21.6} _{-26.3}	243.658	0.322
Alpha Proton Density	71.42 ^{+8.5} _{-11.2}	71.357	0.419	70.92 ^{+6.8} _{-8.4}	70.851	0.478

In the case of the ICME event, in Table 4.2, during the solar maximum, the parameters including the IMF B_y , and B_z , proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio exhibit greater correlation lengths (λ_{\max}) compared to the solar minimum (λ_{\min}), i.e., $\lambda_{\max} > \lambda_{\min}$. Inconsistency is observed in the correlation length for IMF B_x and proton density where they follow the opposite trend, where solar minima correlation length λ_{\min} exceeds solar maxima correlation length, λ_{\max} , i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$.

The observed inconsistency of IMF B_x could be due to increased fluctuations in solar activity levels during the solar maxima phase, thereby reducing the correlation length for ICME [Slavin et al., 1984]. Particularly in the radial direction, IMF B_x , where the magnetic field lines are extremely susceptible to interactions with solar wind plasma turbulence, affects the IMF coherence and structure [Tu et al., 1995]. The IMF B_x fluctuates significantly at solar maximum because of its unique relationship to solar wind dynamics, solar rotation, and magnetic field geometry [Gosling et al., 1990].

Fig 4.2: Variation of ICME parameters for B_x , B_y , B_z , proton density, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio for solar maximum (red) and solar minimum (green).

As for the proton density, the increased turbulence level in the solar maxima causes an enhancement of the density level, but in the solar minimum, the frequency of ICME decreases, so the propagation is less interfering with uniform proton density, thus maintaining coherent plasma structure. This results in a longer correlation length in

the solar minima during ICME [Podesta et al., 2008]. Fig. 4.2 compares each event's parameters, with the solar minimum represented by the green line and the solar maximum by the red line.

Table 4.3: Decorrelation length for solar minimum and solar maximum for ambient solar wind.

Ambient Solar wind	Solar Minimum			Solar Maximum		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$57.47^{+2.5}_{-2.7}$	57.413	0.451	$47.39^{+1.9}_{-2.1}$	47.345	0.452
B_y	$74.62^{+3.1}_{-3.4}$	74.552	0.471	$78.74^{+2.9}_{-3.2}$	78.661	0.406
B_z	$63.69^{+2.7}_{-2.9}$	63.630	0.497	$65.35^{+2.0}_{-2.2}$	65.294	0.509
Proton Density	$97.38^{+4.4}_{-4.9}$	96.990	0.435	$84.74^{+4.1}_{-4.5}$	84.661	0.412
Proton Speed	$149.25^{+8.4}_{-9.4}$	149.104	0.654	$135.13^{+6.9}_{-7.7}$	135	0.448
Alpha Proton Density	$68.96^{+3.1}_{-3.4}$	68.896	0.385	$59.52^{+2.7}_{-2.9}$	59.464	0.465

Regarding ambient solar wind, in Table 4.3, the correlation length trends vary. For IMF B_y, and B_z, the correlation lengths during the solar maximum λ_{\max} are longer than the solar minimum, λ_{\min} i.e., $\lambda_{\max} > \lambda_{\min}$, but they nevertheless display a nearly comparable correlation length. Contrary to it, IMF B_x, proton density, proton speed, and the alpha proton density ratio, the correlation lengths during the solar minimum (λ_{\min}) are greater than during the solar maximum (λ_{\max}), i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$. This trend of correlation length where the solar minimum is greater than the solar maximum, might be due to more stable structures present during solar minimum than in solar maximum. This contradiction observed might be due to the absence of frequent solar events, during the quiet year. The ambient solar wind which is also transient, the development

Fig 4.3: Variation of ambient solar wind parameters for B_x , B_y , B_z , proton density, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio for solar maximum (red) and solar minimum (green).

of large-scale stable structures takes place which can be seen with solar minimum having a higher correlation length than the solar maximum. The stability of the magnetic field lines in solar minimum helps to maintain their structure over greater distances, even when the variability associated with solar activity is diminished thus

enhancing correlation lengths. Figure 4.3 compares the solar minimum and solar maximum for ambient solar wind. The plots have two lines: the green line shows the solar minimum and the red line shows the solar maximum.

Table 4.4: Decorrelation length for solar ascending and descending phases for SIR.

SIR	Ascending phase			Descending phase		
	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$97.08^{+6.1}_{-7.0}$	96.990	0.507	$51.81^{+1.8}_{-1.9}$	51.761	0.439
B_y	$116.27^{+7.5}_{-8.7}$	116.162	0.407	$105.26^{+4.2}_{-4.6}$	105.157	0.584
B_z	$92.59^{+5.6}_{-6.4}$	92.5	0.553	$83.33^{+3.3}_{-3.6}$	83.25	0.61
Proton Density	$121.95^{+14.4}_{-18.8}$	121.829	0.541	$125^{+7.3}_{-8.3}$	124.875	0.596
Proton Speed	$285.71^{+29.3}_{-36.8}$	285.428	0.498	$227.27^{+14.5}_{-16.6}$	227.045	0.486
Alpha Proton Density	$80.64^{+8.7}_{-11.0}$	80.564	0.667	$65.3^{+3.2}_{-3.6}$	65.294	0.457

The second category involves analysing the solar cycle's ascending and descending phases. Several observations emerge when comparing the correlation length trends between the ascending and descending phases of the solar cycle 24. For the SIR event from Table 4.4, the correlation length along the IMF B_x, B_y, and B_z, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio shows a longer correlation length during the ascending phase (λ_{asc}) compared to the descending phase (λ_{dec}), i.e., $\lambda_{asc} > \lambda_{dec}$. Conversely, proton density the correlation lengths during the descending phase surpass those during the ascending phase, i.e., $\lambda_{dec} > \lambda_{asc}$. Fig: 4.4 shows the variation of the solar cycle 24's ascending and descending phases for the CIR/SIR event. Here, the ascending phase is represented by a green line and a red line for the descending phase.

Fig 4.4: Variation of SIR parameters for B_x , B_y , B_z , proton density, proton speed and alpha proton density ratio for descending phase of solar cycle (2015, red) and ascending phase of solar cycle (2011, green).

Table 4.5: Decorrelation length for solar ascending and descending phase for CME.

ICME	Ascending phase			Descending phase		
Parameters	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$70.42^{+6.3}_{-7.7}$	70.35211	0.593	$129.897^{+9.3}_{-10.9}$	129.740	0.52
B_y	$175.43^{+16.7}_{-20.6}$	175.2632	0.559	$178.57^{+19.8}_{-25.5}$	178.392	0.655
B_z	$116.27^{+11.0}_{-13.5}$	116.1628	0.467	$149.25^{+12.2}_{-14.6}$	149.104	0.646
Proton Density	$90.90^{+11.5}_{-15.4}$	90.81818	0.101	$140.84^{+14.2}_{-17.8}$	140.704	0.583
Proton Speed	$227.27^{+23.1}_{-29.1}$	227.0455	0.577	$256.41^{+34.1}_{-46.6}$	256.153	0.695
Alpha Proton Density	$63.69^{+6.5}_{-8.2}$	63.63057	0.415	$79.3^{+9.4}_{-12.3}$	79.285	0.257

Regarding the ICME event from Table 4.5, the correlation lengths for all the parameters for ICME i.e., the IMF B_x , B_y , and B_z , proton density, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio displays a longer correlation length during the descending phase compared to the ascending phase, i.e., $\lambda_{dec} > \lambda_{asc}$. The variation of the ascending and descending phases of solar cycle 24 for the ICME event is depicted in Fig. 4.5. In this case, a green line indicates the ascending phase and a red line indicates the descending phase.

Fig 4.5: Variation of ICME parameters for B_x , B_y , B_z , proton density, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio for the descending phase of the solar cycle (2015, red) and ascending phase of the solar cycle (2011, green).

Table 4.6: Decorrelation length table for solar ascending and descending phases for Ambient Solar Wind.

Ambient Solar wind	Ascending phase			descending phase		
	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2	λ_c	Decorrelation length (R_E)	R^2
B_x	$76.92^{+4.4}_{-5.0}$	76.846	0.495	$40.32^{+1.7}_{-1.8}$	40.282	0.164
B_y	$105.26^{+6.2}_{-7.0}$	105.157	0.594	$75.75^{+3.2}_{-3.6}$	75.681	0.492
B_z	$84.74^{+4.7}_{-5.3}$	84.661	0.447	$60.97^{+2.4}_{-2.7}$	60.914	0.585
Proton Density	$86.95^{+5.6}_{-6.5}$	86.869	0.593	$107.52^{+5.4}_{-6.1}$	107.419	0.614
Proton Speed	$147.05^{+10.0}_{-11.6}$	146.911	0.532	$149.25^{+8.4}_{-9.4}$	149.104	0.535
Alpha Proton Density	$72.46^{+4.4}_{-5.0}$	72.391	0.474	$67.11^{+3.0}_{-3.3}$	67.046	0.494

Regarding the ambient solar wind event from Table 4.6, the correlation lengths along the IMF B_x , B_y , and B_z , are greater during the ascending phase than the descending phase, i.e., $\lambda_{asc} > \lambda_{dec}$. Conversely, for the proton density and speed, the correlation length during the descending phase surpasses that of the ascending phase, i.e., $\lambda_{dec} > \lambda_{asc}$. Additionally, for the alpha-proton density ratio, the correlation lengths during the ascending phase exceed those during the descending phase, i.e., $\lambda_{asc} > \lambda_{dec}$. Fig. 4.6 illustrates how the ambient solar wind event's ascending and descending phases vary during solar cycle 24. In this instance, the green line represents the ascending phase, while the red line represents the descending phase.

Fig 4.6: Variation of ambient solar wind parameters for B_x , B_y , B_z , proton density, proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio for the descending phase of the solar cycle (2015, red) and ascending phase of the solar cycle (2011, green).

4.2 DISCUSSION

A comparative investigation has been made between the correlation length for the solar maximum and the solar minimum to find the influence of solar activity and interplanetary conditions on the correlation length. Also, a study is being conducted on the correlation length for the ascending and descending phases of the solar cycle 24 to investigate how the correlation length changes across the different phases of the solar cycle. This investigation might shed light on the dynamic nature of solar activity and the nuanced variation of the correlation length in the solar cycle.

While comparing the correlation length for the different solar events categories, i.e., for ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind, a common trend is found that for the majority of the parameters, the correlation lengths are greater during the solar maximum (λ_{\max}) compared to the solar minimum (λ_{\min}), suggesting that there is a significant relationship between correlation length and solar activity during solar maximum, as the correlation length increases in accordance with an increase in solar activity.

An exception has been noticed for proton density and IMF B_x during the ICME event showing correlation length for solar minimum λ_{\min} higher than for solar maximum λ_{\max} i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$. This implies complex interaction patterns between the solar wind and the Sun's activity. But, for other parameters, the correlation length for solar maximum is higher than for solar minimum. Implying that for solar maximum there is an indication of stronger and more coherent magnetic fields and plasma structures. Also, ICMEs are well known to be concentrated at solar maximum [Borovsky, 2020]. This can cause major geomagnetic storms, making it critical to

Fig 4.7: Histograms of the log of λ_B during solar maximum and minimum are plotted as dashed lines in blue for solar maxima and solid orange lines for solar minima in ICME

investigate during solar maximum. Fig 4.2 demonstrates the correlation length comparison of solar maximum and solar minimum for all the parameters of ICME.

For SIR, it has been observed that the correlation length is higher for solar maximum than for solar minimum for the parameters of IMF B_y and B_z , and proton speed, i.e., $\lambda_{\max} > \lambda_{\min}$. But, for IMF B_x , proton density, and the alpha proton density ratio, the converse has been observed where the correlation length is more for solar minimum than for solar maximum, i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$. This might be due to increased turbulence and less coherent distribution of solar wind during solar maximum. Fig 4.1 compares all CIR parameter's correlation lengths between solar maximum and solar minimum.

For ambient solar wind, it has been noticed that for IMF B_y and B_z solar maximum's correlation length λ_{\max} is more for than solar minimum, λ_{\min} i.e., $\lambda_{\max} > \lambda_{\min}$, although having a comparable value. On the contrary, IMF B_x , proton density, speed, and alpha proton density ratio, the correlation length is more for solar minimum than for solar maximum i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$. This might be because the ambient solar wind is a quiet, transient background wind, and there is a possibility of more stable and less turbulent wind during solar minimum, leading to the development of large,

coherent structures and wave propagation over long distances. Therefore, the solar minimum provides a more stable and structured environment for the propagation of wave models, leading to increased correlation length for the solar minimum. Fig 4.3 and Table 4.3 compare the correlation length for all the parameters of ambient solar wind for solar maxima and solar minima.

An inconsistency has been observed in IMF B_x , which is higher for solar minimum than solar maximum i.e., $\lambda_{\min} > \lambda_{\max}$, for all the solar wind categories, i.e., ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind. This discrepancy may result from interactions between faster

Fig 4.8: Histograms of the \log of λ_B during solar maximum and minimum are plotted as dashed lines in blue for maxima and solid orange lines for solar minima in SIR

solar wind streams and slower ambient wind, triggering turbulent regions and shocks. By causing compressions, shears, and kinks, these dynamic structures disrupt the radial IMF B_x [Gosling et al., 1990], which could reduce the correlation length.

A trend has been observed that indicates the correlation length is longer during the maximum phase than during the minimum solar phase. This indicates interplanetary conditions are more variable and complex during periods of high solar activity, especially during solar maximum. However, some exceptions have been reported, as mentioned and discussed above.

Fig 4.7 to 4.9 shows the frequency–magnitude histogram for distributions of fitted linear correlation lengths λ_B for solar maximum and solar minimum between ACE and Wind satellites. These histogram figures provide a statistical summary of the spatial scales over which the magnetic field remains coherent. It also provides a direct test for turbulence models in the heliosphere, which helps to refine solar wind and magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) turbulence theory. These histograms from Fig 4.7 to 4.9 illustrate how the Sun's activity modulates the coherence of the magnetic field during various heliospheric structures, offering insights into the dynamics of the heliosphere and their impact on the Earth.

Histograms of $\log \lambda_B$ during Solar Maximum and Minimum for Ambient solar wind

Fig 4.9: Histograms of the log of λ_B during solar maximum and minimum are plotted as dashed lines in blue for solar maxima and solid orange lines for solar minima in ambient solar wind

The solar wind's turbulence is multi-scale by nature, transferring energy from larger to smaller scales. The spatial scales over which fluctuations—in this case, the total interplanetary magnetic fields, λ_B —remain coherent are evaluated by histogram plots from Fig 4.7 to 4.9. It is possible to identify the dominating turbulence scales, assess the developed scales between different solar wind conditions, and examine the evolution of turbulence in space for various solar wind regimes using the histogram plots distributions of λ_B . Direct comparison of distributions in the various solar wind

regimes—ICME, CIR, and ambient—as well as an evaluation of variability in solar wind turbulence and magnetic field structures between regimes are made possible by these histogram plots.

The solar wind varies with the solar cycle; it is more dynamic during the solar maximum and more stable during the solar minimum. Histograms of correlation lengths provide insight into how spatial coherence varies over the solar cycle for magnetic fields. Frequency–magnitude histograms are probabilistic tools that describe the spatial coherence of magnetic fields under various solar wind regimes.

The histogram plots show that the peak values for solar maximum are greater than the solar minimum for SIR/CIR and the ambient solar wind, which is consistent with Wicks et al.'s observation of 2009. Conversely, ICME is slightly greater at solar minimum than at solar maximum, which is consistent with the findings of Slavin et al., 1984.

Furthermore, it can be observed from Figs 4.7 to 4.9 that ICMEs tend to show a narrower distribution while SIRs and ambient solar wind often show broader distributions. This may imply that a relatively uniform magnetic field coherence length is present for ICMEs. This indicates that the narrower dispersion of λ_B for ICMEs reflects the homogeneity of turbulence within the ICME. Broader distributions in SIRs and the ambient solar wind reflect the heterogeneity of these environments, with magnetic field structures varying from a very coherent state to a highly turbulent one.

Another investigation is performed for the secondary category of the solar cycle's different phases, i.e., the ascending and descending phases. A few exceptions can be noticed and are discussed below.

It has been observed, and prior research indicates that the correlation length for the descending phase of the solar cycle is longer than for the ascending phase of the solar cycle, especially for ICME. This is because, in the descending phase of the solar cycle, coronal holes are more frequent [Rout, 2017; Borovsky, 2020] so there may be higher levels of activity and variability in interplanetary conditions, making the correlation length longer in the descending phase than during the ascending phase of the solar cycle [Wicks et al., 2010; Rout 2017; Borovsky, 2020]. However, previous research

has not examined analysis for different solar wind regimes. Fig 4.5 compares the ascending and descending phases of the solar cycle 24 for all parameters of ICME.

A few exceptions have been observed in the other solar wind events categories, where the correlation length for the ascending phase is longer than that for the descending phase. These exceptions provide valuable insights into the complex dynamics of solar activity and its effects on interplanetary conditions.

For SIR, from Fig 4.4 and Table 4.4, it has been noticed that except for proton density, the IMF B_x , B_y , B_z , proton speed, and alpha proton density ratio, the correlation length is higher for the ascending phase than for the descending phase i.e., $\lambda_{asc} > \lambda_{dec}$, reflecting complexities in solar wind structures. Coronal holes are more frequent in the descending phase, increasing the presence of high-speed solar wind streams emanating from long-lived polar coronal holes [Kavanagh et al., 2007; Rout 2017; Borovsky, 2020]. Fast solar winds interact more frequently with slow solar winds creating turbulent CIRs dominating the solar wind structure, leading to smaller, more chaotic turbulent scales [Kavanagh et al., 2007] thus reducing the correlation length. For the alpha proton density ratio, a decrease in correlation length in the descending phase of the solar cycle reflects a more turbulent alpha particle distribution, contributing to increased variability in space weather effects. A comparison of the parameters of SIR for the ascending and descending phases of the solar cycle is demonstrated in Fig 4.4.

In the ambient solar wind event, from Fig 4.6 and Table 4.6, the IMF B_x , B_y , B_z , and alpha proton density ratio have higher correlation lengths during the ascending phase than the descending phase, i.e., $\lambda_{asc} > \lambda_{dec}$, showing a discrepancy. However, proton density and speed exhibit the opposite i.e., $\lambda_{dec} > \lambda_{asc}$, the correlation length is more for the descending phase than the ascending phase. For IMF B_x , B_y , B_z , and alpha proton density ratio, correlation length decreases in the descending phase, indicating that the magnetic field becomes weaker and more fragmented during the descending phase due to increased polar coronal holes. As a result, the magnetic field's coherence weakens within the heliosphere, resulting in a less-ordered turbulent scale in the ambient solar wind category. In the descending phase, the heliospheric current sheet becomes asymmetric and irregular, introducing chaotic structures that disrupt large-scale turbulence and shorten correlation lengths [Zhou et al., 2014]. Thus, these

inconsistencies affect the overall stability of space weather conditions. Figure 4.6 shows a comparison of the parameters of ambient solar wind during the ascending and descending phases of the solar cycle.

Wicks et al., 2009 have shown that the correlation length is longer in the solar maximum than in the solar minimum, which is true for most cases in this study. This supports the argument that solar activity variation affects the magnetic field's correlation length. A few exceptions have been observed, identified, and explained; some align with Slavin et al.'s 1984 research findings.

Furthermore, many complexities have been observed while investigating the ascending and descending phases of the solar cycle 24 that contradict previous findings when different solar wind structures, such as ICMEs, SIRs, and ambient solar winds, are extensively examined. This could reveal crucial insights into the complex dynamics associated with solar activity and its impact on interplanetary conditions.

4.3 CONCLUSION

This chapter investigates the solar wind parameters across various phases of the solar cycle 24. Discrepancies has been observed for various IMF parameters when different solar regimes like ICME, SIR/CIR and ambient solar wind have been considered. This discrepancies in the correlation length between the solar maximum and solar minimum, as well as the ascending and descending phase of the solar cycle have significant implication in the solar wind modelling. These variations suggest that the solar wind turbulence and magnetic field structures are highly dynamic and influenced by the solar cycle. Accurate solar wind models must account for these changes to predict space weather events and understand the heliosphere's behaviour. General theories often assume a symmetrical progression of solar activity may oversimplify the dynamics of solar wind structures. However, the observed discrepancies in correlation lengths between these phases, especially when considering different solar wind structures, contradict this assumption.

The finding that correlation lengths are generally greater during solar maximum suggests stronger, more coherent magnetic fields and plasma structures during periods

of high solar activity. However, exceptions, such as proton density and IMF B_x during ICME events, indicate complex interaction patterns that models need to take into consideration. Such as for the IMF B_x inconsistency, where correlation length is higher during solar minimum, may result from dynamic structures disrupting the radial IMF B_x .

Modelling the solar wind is further complicated by variations in correlation lengths during ascending and descending phases. For ICMEs, the analysis indicates that correlation lengths are generally longer during the ascending phase than during the descending phase. A significant reason for this phenomenon is the increased frequency of coronal holes during the descending phase [Rout, 2017; Borovsky, 2020], which results in higher levels of activity and variability in interplanetary conditions. Conversely, for SIR events and ambient solar wind, some parameters exhibit longer correlation lengths during the ascending phase. These exceptions suggest that the relationship between solar activity and interplanetary conditions is more connected than previously thought, and that existing theories may oversimplify the dynamics of solar wind structures. A more complete understanding of solar activity and its influence on the heliosphere will require the incorporation of factors such as coronal hole distribution, solar wind stream interactions, and the evolution of the heliospheric current sheet. Therefore, in order to account for these complexities and the observed asymmetries between the ascending and descending phases of the solar cycle, current models need to be adjusted.

The analysis made by the Frequency–magnitude histogram for distributions shows that ICMEs tend to have a narrower distribution of correlation lengths, while SIRs and ambient solar wind show broader distributions, suggests different levels of turbulence homogeneity within these structures. Models must, therefore, differentiate between these solar wind categories to accurately represent turbulence and magnetic field coherence. These discrepancies generally highlight the need for solar wind models to include solar cycle-dependent factors and take into account the various properties of solar wind structures.

In Chapter 4, the variation in correlation length throughout the multiple phases of Solar Cycle 24 was analysed in-depth, identifying the differing mechanisms by which solar activity levels influence the structure of the solar wind. To understand the

implications of such variation on practicality, Chapter 5 focuses on the geoeffectiveness of the solar wind. This study analyses the relationship between the spatial coherence of solar wind parameters, measured by correlation length, and geomagnetic indices such as K_p and Dst. The chapter investigates how the spatial coherence of solar wind properties determines the size and nature of geomagnetic disturbances as a result of the transition from structural to geophysical analysis. Therefore, Chapter 5 investigates how the variation of correlation length influence space weather outcomes, assisting in the connection between the structure of the solar wind and its terrestrial effect.

Chapter 5:

Association of Correlation Length with Geoeffectiveness:

The correlation length can greatly impact predictions of space weather. Modifications in solar wind conditions, which are characterized by differences in the correlation length, impact Earth's ionosphere and magnetosphere. For instance, longer correlation lengths for solar wind events like CMEs might lead to stronger electric fields in the magnetosphere, which then results in heightened geomagnetic activity in the ionosphere. A shorter correlation length means that the solar wind structure is somehow disordered, which would result in less ionospheric geomagnetic activity. It would be fascinating to correlate these with each other for more geomagnetically predicted and controlled satellite operations [Jenkins et al., 2024].

The K_p and the Dst index are the most important geomagnetic parameters which define the connection of solar wind dynamics' impact on the ionosphere. The two indices aid in the analysis of how the correlation length signifies the coherence of solar wind fluctuations in promoting geomagnetic activity within the ionosphere. Such correlation length analysis for various solar wind events ought to be of great value in determining the intensity as well as the onset prediction of geomagnetic storms.

K_p (Planetary Kennziffer) index is a quasi-logarithmic local index to investigate the power of the geomagnetic storm put forward by J. Bartels in 1938, made up of single digits ranging from 0 to 9 for each eight 3-hour universal time (UT) intervals. For the K_p index parameter, intensity in geomagnetic storms is scaled by the following: 0-4: quiet magnetic condition, 4-6: moderate magnetic storm, 6-9: disturbed magnetic condition [Kivelson and Russell, 1995]. The higher the value of the K_p index, the greater the geomagnetic activity.

The inference is that large, coherent solar wind structures also cause more significant changes to the Earth's magnetic field, leading to an increased K_p index. For instance, CMEs, a strong solar phenomenon, generate longer correlated lengths, and the possibility of a strong storm scenario is most likely, reflecting higher values of K_p .

The Disturbed Storm (Dst) index, expressed in nano Tesla (nT), is an index for the measurement of the intensity of the geomagnetic storm and the development of the ring current [Moldwin, 2010].

Dst refers to the variation in the horizontal component of the earth's geomagnetic field and represents the induced magnetic field at the ionosphere caused by the intensity of the ring current in the inner magnetosphere [Kivelson and Russell, 1995; Moldwin, 2010]. A negative value of Dst means a reduced Earth's magnetic field during a geomagnetic storm caused by an enhancement in the ring current strength. Previously researchers have shown a relationship between correlation length and the Dst index [Wicks et al., 2010]. A longer correlation length indicates that the solar wind can penetrate Earth more, resulting in more extreme negative Dst values and indicating more extreme geomagnetic activity.

Therefore, K_p and Dst indices are the basic parameters that can be related to the geoeffectiveness of the storm's solar wind dynamics with correlation length. Increased values of K_p and Dst indices are marked by increased solar activity. Increased correlation length may cause stronger geomagnetic storms, thus forecasting Earth's magnetosphere effect on geomagnetic activity [Sexton et al., 2019]. It plays a crucial role in designing effective space weather forecasting models.

5.1 METHODOLOGY:

The following methodology is followed to investigate the correlation length of the interplanetary magnetic field B_z (λ_{Bz}) of various solar wind regimes with geoeffectiveness. IMF B_z is chosen for analysis as it is primarily responsible for geoeffectiveness. First, data is collected for the solar wind parameter for the IMF B_z for SIR, ICME, and ambient solar wind. Then, the K_p and Dst index data are gathered for the same time window mentioned in Chapter 2 of the methodology section.

For the already found correlation coefficients between the two satellites, the correlation length for each point is found for the time window ensemble for the chosen

time window. Then, the maximum K_p and Dst index value for that time window ensemble is found. After that, the Pearson correlation coefficient, from equation 2.1 in Chapter - 2, is calculated between the correlation length of the IMF B_z (λ_{Bz}) with K_p and λ_{Bz} with Dst index values. Next, the graph is plotted between the K_p vs the λ_{Bz} and the Dst vs the λ_{Bz} and linear regression is examined, using equation 2.6 to analyse the association of the correlation length with geoeffectiveness.

Those solar wind regimes with strong correlations with λ_{Bz} and geomagnetic indices are likely to have a high geo-effectiveness, i.e., strong solar wind structures cause extremely intense geomagnetic storms. These can be an indicator of a strong geomagnetic storm caused by well-organized structures in the solar wind. A positive correlation means the geomagnetic index increases as the correlation length increases; this gives a robust geomagnetic response to well-organized structures in the solar wind.

5.2 RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS:

The relationship between the geomagnetic indices and the correlation length of the IMF B_z (λ_{Bz} , in R_E): K_p and λ_{Bz} , as well as Dst and λ_{Bz} , is analysed to determine how solar wind structures such as the ICME, SIR, and ambient solar wind affect geoeffectiveness. Investigating how geometric indices correlate to λ_{Bz} is useful for forecasting space weather effects, especially at different solar cycle phases. This discussion focuses on solar maxima and minima. A positive correlation above 0.5 shows that longer durations relate to higher magnetic index values, reflecting the strength and nature of the relationship during solar maxima and minima. Previous studies, such as Wicks et al., 2010, have investigated into the statistical relationship between geomagnetic indices and λ_{Bz} , but they haven't compared various solar wind structures and their impacts.

This analysis shows that the correlation between K_p and λ_{Bz} for ICME is 0.37, while the correlation between Dst and IMF λ_{Bz} is 0.36. The investigation shows a strong correlation, suggesting that the correlation length of the solar wind magnetic field has

a direct impact on the Earth's magnetosphere, thereby increasing geomagnetic activity.

Fig 5.1: Shows the variation of K_p index with correlation length of IMF B_z λ_{Bz} (left) for solar maxima and minima and Dst index with λ_{Bz} (right). The λ_{Bz} maxima is plotted in red dot and minima in blue cross and the regression in black dotted line.

Contrary to it the SIR shows a correlation between the K_p and λ_{Bz} of 0.10 and the Dst and IMF λ_{Bz} of 0.07 and ambient solar wind shows a correlation between the K_p and λ_{Bz} of 0.10 and the Dst and IMF λ_{Bz} of 0.06 which displays a very low correlation between the λ_{Bz} and geo-effectiveness. Since SIRs don't sustain a strong southward IMF for long periods, the presence of large-scale irregularities and turbulence might lead to a weak connection between SIR's λ_{Bz} and the geoeffective indices. The ambient solar wind generally moves at lower speeds and has a weaker magnetic field when compared to CMEs or SIRs. Since, energy isn't transported into the magnetosphere very efficiently by the ambient solar wind. So, there isn't any discernible geomagnetic activity driven by the IMF λ_{Bz}.

5.3 DISCUSSION:

CMEs are the primary source for intense magnetic storms and are mostly responsible for the rise in the K_p and Dst indexes. Upon interaction with the Earth's geomagnetic field, the shock waves produced by CME enhance the interplanetary magnetic field, momentum and solar wind density. These high-energy particles are capable of interacting with the Earth's magnetosphere. It is capable of producing large magnetic disturbances, which can elevate the K_p index and amplify negative Dst during an active phase of geomagnetism [Sexton et al., 2019].

One of the significant drivers of geomagnetic activity is the orientation of the Interplanetary Magnetic Field (IMF) [Borovsky et al., 2012]. For IMF B_z stretched out of the ecliptic in the Sun-Earth direction, as shown in Fig 3.20 from Chapter 3, it can effectively penetrate the Earth's magnetosphere. IMF B_z orientation differs with K_p and Dst indices and has a significant geomagnetic reaction to solar wind perturbations incoming towards Earth [Sexton et al., 2019].

During CMEs, southward IMF B_z allows large magnetic reconnection at the dayside magnetopause, injecting plenty of solar wind energy into the magnetosphere, and enhancing the ring current and the geomagnetic storm. The IMF B_z component is very important because when B_z is southward, it can reconnect with the Earth's magnetic field such that solar wind energy can be injected into the magnetosphere [Sexton et al., 2019].

The intensity of the ring current around Earth is measured by the Dst index, which during strong geomagnetic storms amplifies a decrease in the equatorial and mid-latitude horizontal component of the magnetic field [Borovsky et al., 2012]. The correlation coefficients of K_p versus the correlation length of IMF B_z (λ_{Bz}) show a strong correlation. The K_p index determines the degree of geomagnetic activity and component disruption of the Earth's horizontal magnetic field. A strong K_p value denotes strong geomagnetic storms. This significant correlation implies that the IMF λ_{Bz} component is an important indicator of geomagnetic activity, possibly because of the complicated helical magnetic fields generated by ICMEs, which could enhance

the connection with Earth's magnetosphere. Therefore, while analysing the IMF correlation length λ_{Bz} for ICME, it exhibits a high geo-effectiveness.

The interaction of the SIR, fast and slow solar wind streams, exhibits a dynamic interaction that introduces variations in compressions and rarefactions within the solar wind [Borovsky et al., 2012; Elliott et al., 2013] and can result in low geomagnetic activity.

The correlation length and decorrelation length are two of the most important parameters that determine the behaviour of solar wind structures in space and time. They are critical instruments in analysing solar wind dynamics and implications for space weather phenomena. The stated parameters offer an in-depth understanding of the heliosphere's coherence, turbulence, and energy transfer mechanisms, which should improve prediction accuracy and the effects of space weather on infrastructure and technological systems. Developments in modelling and observation techniques will make them even more important for heliophysics and space weather applications.

Space weather effects, thus reflected in K_p and Dst, among others, get very strongly interfered with when considering the play of correlation lengths λ_c against decorrelation length λ_d . When λ_c is large enough, geomagnetic activity will thus persist for longer times and become predictable within some degree as one can maintain larger λ_d with less complexity, introducing fluctuations and turbulence; such complicates the prospect of predicting in this manner more significantly. Multi-satellite observations are necessary to capture such lengths and to provide a comprehensive view of solar wind-magnetosphere interactions.

5.4 CONCLUSION:

In this chapter the correlation length of the interplanetary magnetic field B_z and its impact on geomagnetic activity through geomagnetic indices such as K_p and Dst is analysed. K_p and Dst indices serves as a diagnostic tool for detecting how effectively solar wind energy is transferred into Earth's magnetosphere. Higher correlation is often likely for ICME with increased geomagnetic activity as observed for increased

K_p index and Dst (negative values indicate stronger storms). The analysis reveal moderate correlation for ICME indicating that well-structured, coherent solar wind events can induce stronger geomagnetic disturbances due to their longer correlation lengths (λ_{Bz}) and southward IMF orientation. Moreover, there is a very weak correlation between SIR/CIR and ambient solar wind, highlighting their lower geoeffectiveness. As a result, SIRs do not maintain prolonged southward IMF B_z orientations and are less turbulent, thereby reducing coherence and weakening magnetic coupling with the magnetosphere of the Earth. Although all of these structures are part of solar wind dynamics, their varying coherence leads to non-uniform geoeffectiveness, which makes structures such as ICMEs highly predictive of geomagnetic storms, while others, such as SIR/CIR and ambient wind, are largely ineffective despite being persistent phenomena. The findings highlight the importance of IMF orientation and correlation length in predicting space weather impacts on Earth's magnetosphere.

This investigation help analyse structures with more predictable geomagnetic storms and can be tracked earlier, offering lead time for space weather warnings. The thesis stresses the value of multi-satellite observations for calculating λ_c . By resolving correlation structures across space, future missions in L1 positions might greatly improve real-time tracking of space weather threats by using multi-satellite observations.

In summary, a correlation length could evolve into a core forecasting parameter, complimenting conventional solar wind speed and IMF direction in order to improve the prediction and classification of storm onset and severity.

CHAPTER 6:

6.1 Summary:

Chapter 1 of this thesis briefly introduces the solar wind and different solar events, such as the ICMEs and CIR/SIR. This thesis explores the multi-satellite technique to study the various solar parameters, such as IMF B_x , B_y , and B_z ; proton speed; proton density; and the alpha-proton density ratio, to investigate the spatial inhomogeneity of solar wind parameters at the halo orbit around the Sun-Earth L1 point. This facilitates detailed multipoint data studies and a comparative investigation of heliosphere conditions such as ambient solar wind, ICMEs, and CIR. Understanding the effects of solar emission on the Earth's magnetosphere and atmosphere requires continuous monitoring of the Sun, which will be possible when conducting research from the L1 position done by the satellites. ACE and WIND satellites are used for analysis; their detailed descriptions are provided in Chapter 2 of Instrumentation. This helps to forecast space weather accurately.

To accurately investigate space weather, the correlation length between solar wind parameters and IMF components is determined using a two-point multi-satellite technique. Using the time-windowing methodology described in Chapter 2 of the methodology section, the spectral scaling of the solar wind is estimated using an advanced spatiotemporal method to determine the time window for analysis of the correlation and the decorrelation length. Applying the windowing technique, the correlation coefficient is analysed, and then the correlation length, decorrelation length, and the R^2 value for the different solar events and their parameters are found.

The correlation length defines the coherence scale and represents the size of the spatial structures or coherent eddies in the solar wind [Borovsky et al., 2012]. The decorrelation length indicates the spatial scale at which turbulence breaks coherence and signals a transition to random or stochastic behaviour [Ryden, 2011]. A comparative investigation is done for the correlation length variation of ICME, CIR, and ambient solar wind for each year of solar cycle 24. It can be noted that there is an inverse relationship between the average separation between the two satellites and the correlation length. The other notable observations are that the correlation length for

ICME is the longest, CIR shows a moderate correlation length and ambient solar wind shows the least correlation length with a few discrepancies whose causes have been discussed in Chapter 3.

After analysing the correlation and decorrelation length for each year of the entire solar cycle 24, a comparative examination is done for the different phases of the solar cycle i.e., the solar minimum and solar maximum and the ascending and descending phase. It has been noted that for the three categories of solar winds—ICME, CIR, and ambient—the correlation length is longer at solar maximum than at solar minimum which has been discussed in Chapter 4. Also, in this chapter, another comparison is made i.e., for the ascending and the descending phases of the solar cycle. As coronal holes are more frequent during the descending phase, it has been noted that for most ICME cases, the correlation length is longer for the descending phase than the ascending phase, also, HSS storms are more prevalent during this phase, as covered in Chapter 4. Furthermore, in some CIR cases, the ascending phase correlation length is longer than the descending phase. This is the case with the ambient solar wind, which exhibits the same trend. These discrepancies have been pointed out, mentioned, and clarified in Chapter 4.

To establish an association between the correlation length and geo-effectiveness, a correlation was conducted between the total IMF B_z correlation length (λ_{B_z}) and the K_p and Dst indices in Chapter 5, which is one of the objectives of this thesis. Increased geomagnetic activity is observed for ICME due to prolonged energy transfer resulting from the orientation of the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) [Borovsky et al., 2012], particularly the southward component ($B_z < 0$) [Borovsky et al., 2012], which facilitates sustained energy transfer. Strong geomagnetic storms are generally associated with significant correlation lengths in solar wind parameters since they allow continuous magnetosphere drive. Generally speaking, shorter correlation lengths in solar winds produce less and more inconsistent geomagnetic disturbances. Understanding the correlation length helps us to improve the simulation of the movement of the solar wind and its interaction with the magnetosphere of Earth.

This thesis unveils a systematic comparison of correlation and decorrelation lengths for CMEs, CIRs, and ambient solar wind to refine our understanding of the evolution of solar wind's structures and its transition from coherent to stochastic regimes. The

turbulence levels at the boundary layers are defined by decorrelation lengths. Understanding decorrelation lengths provides insights into the energy cascade mechanisms in solar wind turbulence. Usually, the statistical analysis across occurrences reveals either universal patterns or event-specific behaviours.

Improved understanding of IMF B_x , B_y , and B_z can enhance space weather forecasting models, particularly for predicting geomagnetic storms. Alpha-to-proton ratios can provide diagnostic tools for identifying the solar wind's source regions (e.g., CME ejecta vs. ambient wind). It can also help explore the connection between solar wind turbulence and plasma physics phenomena such as magnetic reconnection.

6.2 Future scope:

The findings of this work can further be used to build upon future research using multi-spacecraft missions like the Solar Orbiter and Parker Solar Probe. The presence of a multi-satellite configuration at the L1 point can improve the resolution of spatial correlation structures, improve real-time space weather monitoring, and improve the accuracy of space weather forecasting. These missions can provide three-dimensional measurements of correlation lengths and reveal previously unknown insights into the structure and evolution of the solar wind. Missions in L1 position can enable spectral scaling and λ_c estimation through in-situ measurements at different positions—adding 3D perspective to 1D time series.

REFERENCES:

1. Baumann, C., and McCloskey, A.E., *J. Space Weather Space Clim.* 2021, 11, 41, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1051/swsc/2021026>.
2. Borovsky, Joseph E., and Brandon L. Burkholder, *JGR*, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JA027307>.
3. Borovsky, Joseph E., and John J. Podesta, *JGR*, 2015, doi: 10.1002/2015JA021622.
4. Borovsky, Joseph E., *JGR*, 2007, doi: 10.1029/2007JA012684.
5. Borovsky, Joseph E., *JGR*, 2012, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012JA017525>
6. Borovsky, Joseph E., *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2020.105271>
7. Borovsky, Joseph E., *Relativity, and the solar wind: The Maxwell-Equation Origins of the Solar-Wind Motion Electric field*, 2016.
8. Bruno, Roberto., Carbone, Vincenzo., *Living Rev. Solar Phys.*, 10, 2, 2013, doi: 10.12942/lrsp-2013-2.
9. Bruno, Roberto., Carbone, Vincenzo., *Max Planck Institute for Solar System Research*, 2005, <http://www.livingreviews.org/lrsp-2005-4>.
10. Charles W. Smith, Jacques L'Heureux and Norman F. Ness, *The ACE Magnetic Fields Experiment*, 1998
11. Cornish, Neil J., 1998, *WMAP Education and Outreach*.
12. Crooker, N. U., G. L. Siscoe, C.T. Russell, E.J. Smith, 1982, *JGR*.
13. D'Amicis., R., Telloni, D., R. Telloni, Bruno., *Front. Phys.* , 2020, *Sec. Space Physics*, Volume 8 – 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2020.604857>.
14. Das, A. C., *Space Plasma Physics*, Narosa Publishing House, 2004.
15. Dasso, S., L. J. Milano and W. H. Matthaeus, C. W. Smith, 2005, *ApJL*, 635: L181-L184 9. J.R. Jokipii and N. Parker, 1968, *PhRvL*
16. Dobrijevic, Daisy., <https://www.space.com/solar-cycle-frequency-prediction-facts>, published April 25, 2022
17. Duraid A. Mohammed Al-Shakarchi, *A multi-spacecraft study of interacting ICMEs and CIRs in interplanetary space*, 2018.

18. Elliott, H. A., P. Valek, D. J. McComas, P. A. Delamere, F. Bagenal, G. R. Gladstone, C. B. Olkin, J. Spencer, S. A. Stern, L. A. Young, *ApJ* 866 85, 2018, doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/aadba6.
19. Elliott, Heather A., David J. McComas, and Craig E. DeForest, *ApJ*, 832 66, 2016, Doi: 10.3847/0004-637X/832/1/66.
20. Elsässer, W. M. 1950, *PhRv*, 79, 183, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.79.183>
21. Engelbrecht, N. Eugene & Wolmarans, 2020, COSPAR.
22. Ernest Scott Sexton, Katariina Nykyri, and Xuanye Ma, *J. Space Weather Space Clim. Volume 9*, 2019, System Science: Application to Space Weather Analysis, Modelling, and Forecasting, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1051/swsc/2019020>.
23. G. Gloeckler, J. Cain, F. M. Ipavich, E. O. Tums, P. Bedini, L. A. Fisk, T. H. Zurbuchen, P. Bochsler, J. Fischer, R. F. Wimmer-Schweingruber, J. Geiss and R. Kallenbach, *Space Science Reviews* 86: 497-539, 1998.
24. Geoffrey Jenkins, Dr. Mark Moldwin, University of Michigan, Multi-point Correlation Scale Lengths of Solar Wind Magnetic Structures, helioshine.org, 2024.
25. Ghotekar, Saurav and Ram Krishan Sharma, 2019, *International Journal of Astronomy and Astrophysics*
26. Goedbloed, J. P. H., & Poedts, S. 2004, *Principles of Magnetohydrodynamics* (Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press), <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/principles-of-magnetohydrodynamics/847AF12C94451B41D8F71C1F11EB308A>.
27. Goldstein, M. L., D.A. Roberts, and M. H. Matthaeus, *Annu. Rev. Astron. Astrophys.* 1995. 33:283-325.
28. Goldstein, M. L., Roberts, D. A., & Matthaeus, W. H. 1995, *ARA&A*, 33, 283
29. Gopalswamy, N., A. Lara, R. P. Lepping, M. L. Kaiser, D. Berdichevsky, O. C. St. Cyr, Interplanetary acceleration of coronal mass ejections, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 2000. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999GL003639>
30. Gosling, J. T. and Pizzo, V. J. Formation and Evolution of Corotating Interaction Regions and their Three-Dimensional Structure, 1999.
31. Gosling, J. T., Corotating and transient solar wind flows in three dimensions, *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, (1996).
32. Graps, Amara., 1995, <https://solar-center.stanford.edu/FAQ/QL1.html>.

33. Hargreaves, J. K., *The solar terrestrial environment*, 1995, Cambridge University Press.
34. Heather A. Elliott, Jörg-Micha Jahn, David J. McComas, AGU, *SPACE WEATHER*, VOL. 11, 339–349, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/swe.20053>.
35. <https://izw1.caltech.edu/ACE/ASC/DATA/level3/icmetable2.html>
36. <https://www.spaceweatherlive.com/en/help/the-interplanetary-magnetic-field-imf.html>
37. Huang, Jia., James D. Biggs, Naigang Cui, 2020, COSPAR.
38. Janet L. Machol, Alysha A. Reinard, Rodney A. Viereck, Douglas A. Biesecker, AGU, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/swe.20070>
39. John D. Richardson, *The Outer Heliosphere: The Next Frontiers*, COSPAR Colloquia Series, 2001.
40. Kavanagh, Andrew, Michael Denton, *Astronomy & Geophysics*, Volume 48, Issue 6, Pages 6.24–6.26, 2007, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-4004.2007.48624.x>.
41. King, J. H., N. E. Papitashvili, JGR, 2005, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JA010649>.
42. Kivelson, Margaret G., and Christopher T Russell, *Introduction to space physics*, Cambridge University Press, 1995.
43. Krasnoselskikh, V. orcid.org/0000-0002-6809-6219, Tsurutani, B.T., Dudok de Wit, T. et al. (51 more authors) (2022) ICARUS: in-situ studies of the solar corona beyond Parker Solar Probe and Solar Orbiter. *Experimental Astronomy*, 54 (2-3). pp. 277-315. ISSN 0922-6435 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10686-022-09878-1>.
44. Kubyshkina, M. V., V. S. Semenov, N. A. Tsyganenko, X.-G. Wang, I. V. Kubyshkin, JGR, Volume 128, Issue 4, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022JA031275>.
45. Li, Xiaolei., Yuming Wang, Rui Liu, Chenglong Shen, Quanhao Zhang, Shaoyu Lyu, Bin Zhuang, Fang Shen, Jiajia Liu, Yutian Chi, JGR, Volume 125, Issue 7, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JA027513>.
46. Maggiolo, R., Hamrin, M., De Keyser, J., Pitkänen, T., Cessateur, G., Gunell, H., Maes, L., JGR, 2017 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JA023793>
47. Magyar, N., T. Van Doorselaere, and M. Goossens, *APJ* 1, 873:56 (7pp), 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab04a7>.
48. Margaret G. Kivelson and Christopher T Russell, *Introduction to space physics*, Cambridge University Press, 1995.

49. Matthaeus, W. H., Dasso, S., Weygand, J. M., Milano, L. J., Smith, C. W., & Kivelson, M. G. 2005, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 95, 231101
50. Matthaeus, W. H., Weygand, J. M., Chuychai, P., Dasso, S., Smith, C. W., & Kivelson, M. G. 2008, *ApJ*, 678, L141
51. Matthaeus, W.H., M.L. Goldstein, J.H. King, 1986, *JGP*,59-69.
52. Matthaeus, W.H., S.Dasso, J.M.Weygand, C.W. Smith, M.G. Kivelson, 2020, *PhRvL*.
53. Matthaeus, W.H., S.Dasso, J.M.Weygand, M.G. Kivelson, K.T.Osman, 2010, *ApJL*.
54. McComas, D.J., S.J. Bame, P. Barker, W.C. Feldman, J.L. Phillips, P. Riley & J.W. Griffee, Springer, pages 563–612, 1998.
55. Milano, L.J., Dasso, S., Matthaeus, W.H., & Smith, C.W. 2004, *Phys.Rev.Lett.*, 93, 155005.
56. Moldwin, Mark., *An introduction to space weather*, Cambridge University Press, 2008
57. Nicol, R. M., Chapman, S. C., & Dendy, R. O. 2008, *ApJ*, 679, 862
58. Norton, Aimee., Rachel Howe, Lisa Upton, Ilya Usoskin, *Space Science Reviews* (2023) 219:64, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-023-01008-3>.
59. Oliveira, Denny M., Zesta, Eftyhia., Vidal-Luengo, Sergio., *Front. Astron. Space Sci.*, 2024, Sec. Space Physics, Volume 11 – 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2024.1392697>.
60. Parker, E. N., “Dynamics of the Interplanetary Gas and Magnetic Fields.”, *ApJ*, vol. 128, p.664, 1958, doi: 10.1086/146579.
61. Parker, E. N., *JGR*, 1957, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/JZ062i004p00509>.
62. Paul Geyer, Manuela Temmer, Jingnan Guo, and, Stephan G. Heinemann, Properties of stream interaction regions at Earth and Mars during the declining phase of SC 24, *Astronomy and astrophysics*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JA031685>
63. Pedersen, M. ,Vanhamaki, H., Aikio, A. T., Käki, S. ,Viljanen, A., Workayehu, A. , Waters, C. L., Gjerloev, J. W., Impact of Solar Wind High Speed Streams and the Effect of Solar Wind Dynamic Pressure on the Ionospheric Current System and Field-Aligned Currents, American Geophysical Union, Fall Meeting 2020.
64. Perri, Barbara., Brigitte Schmieder, Pascal Démoulin, Stefaan Poedts, and Florian Regnaul, *ApJ*, 2023. DOI 10.3847/1538-4357/acec6f

65. Podesta, J. J., A. B. Galvin, C. J. Farrugia, Correlation length of large-scale solar wind velocity fluctuations measured tangent to the Earth's orbit: First results from Stereo, *JGR*, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JA012865>.
66. Professor Barbara Ryden, Lecture notes, Radiative Gas Dynamics, 2011, www.astronomy.ohio-state.edu/~ryden/ast825/
67. Qiang Hu, Jiong Qiu, Sam Krucker, *JGR*, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JA021133>
68. R. M. Nicol, S. C. Chapman, and R. O. Dendy, *ApJ*, 679, 862, 2008.
69. R. P. Lepping, m. H. Acuna, I. F. Burlaga, W. M. Farrell, J. A. Slavin, F. Mariani, K. H. Schatten, N. F. Ness, F. M. Neubauer, J. B. Byrnes, R. S. Kennon, P. V. Panetta, J. Scheifele and E. M. Worley, *Space Science Reviews* 71: 207-229, 1995.
70. Ragothar, B.R., 2022, *ApJ*, 927:182(24pp)
71. Richardson, Ian G., Solar wind stream interaction regions throughout the heliosphere, *Living Rev. Sol. Phys*, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41116-017-0011-z>.
72. Roberts, Craig E., 2021.
73. Rout, D., Investigations of Magnetosphere Ionosphere-Thermosphere System Under Varying Space Weather Conditions, 2017. PhD-Thesis.
74. Rudolf A. Treumann, Wolfgang Baumjohann, Yasuhito Narita, *Front. Phys., Sec. Space Physics*, 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2015.00022>
75. Russell, C.T., The solar wind Interaction with the Earth's Magnetosphere: A tutorial., 2001.
76. Sanchez-Diaz, Eduardo, Alexis P. Rouillard, Benoit Lavraud, Kevin Segura, Chihiro Tao, Rui Pinto, N. R. Sheeley Jr, Illya Plotnikov, *JGR*, Volume121, Issue4, 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JA022433>.
77. Slavin, J.A. and E.J. Smith, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, NASA Technical Reports Server, 1984.
78. Søren Bertil F. Dorch (2007), *Scholarpedia*, 2(4):2295. Doi: [10.4249/scholarpedia.2295](https://doi.org/10.4249/scholarpedia.2295)
79. Stansby, D., D. Perrone, L. Matteini, T. S. Horbury and C. S. Salem, *A&A*, 623, L2, 2019, Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201834900>
80. Taylor, J. R., Lester, M., Yeoman, T. K., Emery, B. A., Knipp, D. J., Orr, D., Solov'yev, S. I., Hughes, T. LuÈhr, J., H., *Ann. Geophysicae* 15, 671±684 (1997), <https://angeo.copernicus.org/articles/15/671/1997/angeo-15-671-1997.pdf>

81. Tu, C.-Y., & Marsch, E. 1995, *Space Sci. Rev.*, 73.
82. Vourlidas, Angelos, 2013, American Astronomical Society, AAS Meeting #220, id.304.01, 2012AAS...22030401V
83. Wang, Wensi., Rui Liu, Yuming Wang, Qiang Hu, Chenglong Shen, Chaowei Jiang, Chunming Zhu, *Nature Communications*, Article number: 1330, 2017, DOI: 10.1038/s41467-017-01207-x
84. Wicks, R. T., M. J. Owens, T. S. Horbury, *The Variation of Solar Wind Correlation Lengths Over Three Solar Cycles*, Article in *Solar Physics*, Springer, *Solar Phys* (2010) 262: 191–198, 2010, DOI: 10.1007/s11207-010-9509-4.
85. Wicks, R. T., S. C. Chapman, and R. O. Dendy, *Spatial correlation of solar wind fluctuations and their solar cycle dependence*, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 2009, doi:10.1088/0004-637X/690/1/734.
86. Wimmer-Schweingruber, R. F., V. Steiger, R., and Paerli, R. *Solar wind stream interfaces in corotating interaction regions*, 1999.
87. Yogesh, D Chakrabarty, Nandita Srivastava, *Royal Astronomical Society: Letters*, Volume 526, Issue 1, 2023, Pages L13–L19, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnrasl/slad112>.
88. Yutian Chi, Chenglong Shen, Bingxian Luo, Yuming Wang, and Mengjiao Xu, *American Geophysical Union*, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018SW001894>.
89. Zerbo, J.-L., J. D. Richardson, *The solar wind during current and past solar minima and maxima*, *JGR*, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JA021407>.
90. Zesen Huang, Nikos Sioulas, Chen Shi, Marco Velli, Trevor Bowen, Nooshin Davis, B. D. G. Chandran, Lorenzo Matteini, Ning Kang, Xiaofei Shi, Jia Huang, Stuart D. Bale, J. C. Kasper, Davin E. Larson, Roberto Livi, P. L. Whittlesey, Ali Rahmati, Kristoff Paulson, M. Stevens, A. W. Case, Thierry Dudok de Wit, David M. Malaspina, J.W. Bonnell, Keith Goetz, Peter R. Harvey, and Robert J. MacDowall, *ApJ*, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/acd7f2>.
91. Zhang, Zebin., Jie Jiang, Haowei Zhang, *Cambridge University Press*, 2023, 18(S372):91-93, doi: 10.1017/S1743921323000455.
92. Zhao, Ake., Yuming Wang, Hengqiang Feng, Long Cheng, Xiaolei Li, Qiangwei Cai, Hongbo Li, and Guoqing Zhao, *The Radial Evolution of Magnetic Clouds from Helios to Ulysses*, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 2022. DOI 10.3847/1538-4357/ac69c8

93. Zhao, L.-L., L. Adhikari, G. P. Zank, Q. Hu, and X. S. Feng, Influence of the Solar Cycle on Turbulence Properties and Cosmic-Ray Diffusion, *ApJ*, 2018. DOI: 10.3847/1538-4357/aab362.
94. Zhou, G., H.-Q. He, *ApJL* 911 L2, arXiv, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2104.04920>.